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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Communication is a central component of preparing for, responding to and recovering from a crisis. Accordingly, the purpose of this report is to provide a baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications to be used in crisis management activities. By doing this preparatory task, the COSMIC consortium are able to help provide recommendations to stakeholders in subsequent work packages on how to most effectively utilise new information and communication technology. The report contains five chapters.

Chapter 1 contains an introduction to the report, providing readers with a clear rationale for carrying out this preparatory task, and provides a distinction between existing communication technologies and new media applications. The chapter emphasises the importance of vital functionality, particularly in enabling two-way communication, stemming from advances in new media, contributing to the “social” element of new media applications.

Chapter 2 analyses the state of the art of communication technology in the context of crisis management. It discusses telecommunication technologies as products that are ready to be deployed, and as technology components and services that can be used or further developed. These technologies can often be developed in conjunction with other components and services in order to enable the overall functionality required in a specific crisis management scenario. The analysis includes a discussion of the functional and non-functional requirements of technologies, and the advanced capabilities that modern communication technology can provide. Furthermore it assesses how stakeholders can assess telecommunication technologies for user and application needs. The chapter also considers the important issue of interoperability. The chapter concludes by briefly highlighting trends in case studies relating to the capabilities of new media applications and relevant statistics relating to the adoption of some communication technologies.

Chapter 3 provides a baseline analysis of new media applications that partners have found to have been used in crisis management activities. Findings from this chapter show how new media applications provide visual information as well as the ability to enable users to interact and share information with other users. These applications range from social networking websites to tailor-made crisis management tools and applications. Combined, these tools provide various stakeholders with the opportunity to co-ordinate and collaborate to respond to an emerging crises, as well as preparing for future crises. Crucially, this chapter highlights the functionality of different application for the purpose of crisis management.

Chapter 4 identifies which “known” stakeholders are using new media applications as part of their crisis management activities. The chapter shows that five types of stakeholders are using new media applications: Government, the media, civil society organisations, industry and the public. A crucial finding of this chapter regards the (current) lack of primary data freely available to determine how some new media applications, particularly mobile applications, for crisis management are being used, thus making it somewhat difficult to fully understand stakeholder use of new media applications. Partners will seek to further understand stakeholder use in Tasks 2.2 of this work package that will seek to conduct in-depth case studies of new media use in crisis situations. Finally, the chapter shows that some of the web based applications and social networking applications were not originally developed to aid crisis response, however, their features are becoming popular tools for crisis management activities.

The report concludes in Chapter 5, the conclusion by synthesising the findings of the previous chapters and considering the next steps for the COSMIC project.

1 INTRODUCTION

Communication is a critical component of preparing for, responding to and recovering from crises.¹ As stated by the International Telecommunications Union (ITU):

Telecommunications are indispensable tools for the operational emergency management. The speed of response and, most of all, the appropriateness of such response, depend on the real-time exchange of information among a multitude of partners. Reliable telecommunications are also a prerequisite for the safety and security of those who often risk their own life in their efforts to save lives and to alleviate the suffering caused by disasters. Last but not least, success in mobilizing of resources depends to a large degree on the quality of reporting from the site of an event.²

The tools that stakeholders can use are no longer limited to the use of conventional telecommunications technologies, such as the telephone or radio, but has expanded to a host of new media applications. Accordingly, COSMIC aims to understand the most effective ways of utilising new information and communication technologies (ICT's) in crisis situations so as to enhance the protection of ordinary citizens. In order to complete this objective, the consortium must identify those new information and communication technologies that are available to stakeholders.

Whilst work package (WP) 3 focuses on mapping the use of emerging technologies, WP2, of which this report stems from, will map the use of existing technologies. By doing so, the COSMIC project will be able to base its recommendations of the most effective ways of using ICT's in crisis situations on those ICT's that are well situated within crisis management, as well as those that are emerging and may present new opportunities for crisis management.

The purpose of the present report, Deliverable 2.1, is to provide a baseline analysis of communication technologies and applications that are currently available and in use within crisis response. In order to do so, partners have split the work between two tasks: 1) an exploration of the state of the art of communication technologies, and 2) an exploration of the state of the art in new media applications. By doing so, partners will be able identify further information on ICT's and new media applications that are available for crisis management. Partners will also detail existing stakeholder use of these new media applications. This will be further supplemented by deliverable 2.2 “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, thereby enabling partners to provide an in-depth understanding of the use of current technologies in crises. The findings of both deliverables will be used to develop a briefing paper on new media in crisis situations (Deliverable 2.4).

First however it is necessary to distinguish between ICT's and new media applications.

1.1 ICT VS. NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS

Information communication technology (ICT) refers to those technologies that provide individuals with access to information through telecommunications.³ Telecommunications

¹ ITU, *Handbook on Emergency Telecommunications*, International Telecommunications Union, Switzerland, 2005.

² Ibid., p. 23.

³ Christensson, Per, “ICT”, *TechTerms*, 4 January 2010. <http://www.techterms.com/definition/ict>

refer to the “transmission of signals over long distances”. Although earlier experimentations with communication with electricity date back to early 18th century, the first telecommunication system that gained widespread adoption was the telegraph, which often is credited to Samuel Morse’s work in 1830’s and 1840’s. Since then, telecommunications technologies have come to encompass a wide range of technologies like the telephone, radio and television broadcasts, digital satellites, the Internet, and mobile networks.⁴

Within the field of emergency communications, as identified by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), there are a range of ICTs that stakeholders can use to prepare and respond to emergencies, these include, but are not restricted to; Public switched telephone network, mobile phones, satellite terminals and satellite phones, the Internet, radio, broadcasting and new technologies.⁵ As will be explored in Chapter 3, different technologies provide different functions within the management of crises.

Advances in information technologies have contributed to the development of what is known as new media. Although not easy to define, Manovich breaks new media down into distinct components that are central to our understanding of the uniqueness of new media, as opposed to ICT’s that are predominantly focused around telecommunications.⁶ For instance, as outlined by Manovich, it is essential to consider new media as a form of computer technology; it is a cultural object “which uses digital computer technology for distribution and exhibition”.⁷ New media is made up of digital data that can be “controlled by software”⁸, by doing so new media can manipulate data in a much faster way using algorithms to alter the appearance or original use of the data.⁹

Elsewhere, Flew makes the point that there are three C’s to new media: computing and information technology, communication networks and digitised media content which stems from convergence; that is the combination of computing, communications and (digital) content. For Flew, it is important to consider the “digital” element of new media, which includes the combination of “integrate data, text, sound and image of all kinds...stored in digital formats, and are increasingly distributed through networks”.¹⁰ For crisis management, new media is of particular interest due to its ability to enable a more “social” form of communication of various digital objects. In particular, some new media applications allow for greater interaction and the ability to edit and share digital data between users.

A vital function stemming from advances in new media are those applications that are inherently “social” as a result of advances in a particular type of new media; Web2.0 applications. Web 2.0 refers to the increase in applications on the Internet that enable public collaboration and the sharing of information. According to Beer and Burrows, the expansion of public involvement in Web 2.0 is largely linked to the development and global popularity of social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter.¹¹ Central to the popularity of web

⁴ Christensson, Per, “Telecommunications”, *TechTerms*, 14 April 2009.

<http://www.techterms.com/definition/telecommunications>

⁵ For a comprehensive guide to telecommunications in emergency management see: ITU, 2005.

⁶ Manovich, Lev, “New Media from Borges to HTML”, in Wardrip-Fruin, Noah, and Nick Montfort, *The New Media Reader*, MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass., 2003.

⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 17.

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 17.

⁹ For a more extensive understanding of the technical functionality of new media, please see Manovich, 2003.

¹⁰ Flew, T, *New Media: An Introduction*, Open University Press, Australia, 2008. [pp. 3-5]

¹¹ Beer, D. and Burrows, R, “Sociology and, of and in Web 2.0: Some Initial Considerations”, *Sociological Research Online*, Vol. 12, No. 5, 2008, p.1-15.

2.0 is the willing involvement and participation of individuals in using these applications, thereby making them useful in a range of situations.

Accordingly, in Chapter 4, our baseline analysis of new media applications in crisis management will identify and describe various applications that enable a more “social” approach to information sharing in their functionality, and therefore what this social way of communicating can contribute to crisis management.

1.2 REPORT STRUCTURE

This report consists of four additional chapters. Chapter 2 provides a baseline analysis of the state of the art in communication technologies (e.g., radios, mobile and land-line telephone, the Internet) that are currently being used by users across the globe. The chapter examines functionality, non-functionality and interoperability of telecommunications. The chapter also examines how telecommunications can meet user needs.

Similar to Chapter 2, Chapter 3 of this report will provide a baseline analysis of the state of the art in new media applications that are currently being used to help stakeholders prepare, respond, and in some cases, recover from crises. Chapter 3 will explore four primary forms of new media applications; social networking applications, web based tools, crowdsourcing applications and mobile applications. The chapter will seek to provide some brief explanatory information about each application, it will also identify how these applications can be accessed, and crucially, partners will identify the functionality of each application (i.e., how they contribute to crisis management).

Chapter 4 of this report entails an exploration of key stakeholders and usage trends of new media applications in crisis management. Where possible, partners will identify which stakeholders are using different types of new media applications.

The report will conclude in chapter 5 by synthesising findings from previous chapters and considering how the findings of this report will complement the efforts of partners in future deliverables of the COSMIC project.

2 STATE OF THE ART OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY FOR CRISIS MANAGEMENT

This chapter analyses the state of the art of communication technology in the context of crisis management. It begins with a brief discussion of communication technologies within crisis management, examining trends and general considerations. Following this, the authors describe existing capabilities; we list functional and non-functional requirements that should be considered in contemplating the use of communication technology in the context of crisis management. Authors also identify and briefly discuss specific communication technology products that can be used for crisis management. Authors then discuss a general framework for assessing communication technology in the context of crisis management, which is useful considering the advances in communication technologies in comparison to those that dominated for the majority of the 20th century. The chapter concludes by briefly considering relevant case studies relating to the use of communication technologies in crisis situations as well as by considering statistics relating to the proliferation of digital communication technologies in various regions of the world.

2.1 COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Information Communication Technologies (ICT) are revolutionising crisis management^{12,13,14}. Some of the ways in which this is happening are not surprising given the capabilities of modern telecommunications. Citizen first responders are able to communicate in real-time and on the move. They can now share valuable information and coordinate their actions far more effectively than previously possible. Citizens needing help can also communicate in the same way, providing information on their location, status and needs. Government and NGO first responders already used radio links for voice communications, but now they can also, as mentioned, communicate with those in need of help much more efficiently. They can share data amongst themselves, such as images and videos, and they can use a variety of information providing applications.¹⁵

Innovative uses of modern telecommunications capabilities are also being discovered. For example, new commercial platforms can offer better interoperability than previous-generation mission-critical grade telecommunications systems.¹⁶ During a crisis, as will be discussed further in Chapter 3, social networking sites emerge as heavily-used systems for broadcasting information to citizens, competing with conventional television and radio. After the

¹² Jones, V. M., G. Karagiannis, and SM Heemstra de Groot. "Support for Resilient Communications in Future Disaster Management." *Computer and Information Sciences II*. Springer London, 2012, pp. 355-359.

¹³ Jenkins, William O. *Emergency Communications: Establishment of the Emergency Communications Preparedness Center and Related Interagency Coordination Challenges*. DIANE Publishing, 2010.

¹⁴ *Humanitarianism in the Network Age: Including World Humanitarian Data and Trends 2012*, Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), 2013.

¹⁵ Haddon, Leslie. *Information and communication technologies in everyday life: A concise introduction and research guide*. Berg, 2004

¹⁶ Mission-critical grade telecommunications systems are telecommunications systems that can be relied upon in cases where their correct functioning is an essential requirement for a successful operation. For example, mission-critical grade telecommunications systems must provide rugged devices capable of functioning in an unfavourable environment, e.g. in the rain or at very high temperatures. Other definitions: mission-critical: (of hardware or software) vital to the functioning of an organization [<http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/mission--critical>]; Definition of 'Mission Critical': An activity, device, service or system whose failure or disruption will cause a failure in business operations [<http://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/mission-critical.asp>]

development of custom solutions for mission-critical grade telecommunications such as TETRA¹⁷ (primarily in the EU) and P25 (primarily in the US) in the evolution beyond analogue radio communications, the current trend is to extend the commercial standard LTE to encompass mission-critical grade systems.¹⁸ In other words, it is more effective to take advantage of the functional benefits of a commercial solutions by enhancing the standard to satisfy mission-critical non-functional requirements, rather than build a custom solution satisfying mission-critical non-functional requirements and develop its functional aspects so as to keep up with the applications supported by commercial telecommunications systems. This is in evidence in the aforementioned trend to abandon TETRA and P25 in favour of a future version of LTE.

The degree of choice in utilisation of communication technologies when preparing for effective crisis management may be limited by a variety of factors. Government and non-governmental organisation (NGO) planners and field personnel may be limited by their internal policies. Even at an organisational level, constraints such as interoperability are likely to guide technological choices, even if such choices are not formally prescribed by legal or national policy requirements. Finally, mission-critical grade telecommunications options tend to offer particular benefits over mainstream commercial solutions (for example, mission-critical grade two-way radio can operate in harsh environmental conditions and in areas not covered by telecommunications infrastructure) but will tend to be more expensive and to offer more limited overall capabilities.

The speed of technological change has become a major factor in the emergency communications landscape. There have been rapid innovations creating more valuable capabilities that can increase the effectiveness of crisis management, saving lives, and protecting the environment and property^{19,20}. However, there are also mission-critical grade technologies that are unable to keep up with commercial technologies: first, the scale of effort being invested in developing new commercial capabilities has become very difficult to compete with; second, the technological innovation-to-obsolescence lifecycle has become so rapid that typical mission-critical grade technology standardisation processes may well standardise a technology only after it is already obsolete; and third, the rapidly evolving commercial telecommunications environment defines the context in which Government and NGO organisations need to interact, e.g. in order to communicate with citizens.

Long-standing assumptions about communications channels are also being challenged and can become invalid faster than safety and other policies can evolve to track them. For example, as citizens turn away from “traditional” “copper-wire” land-line telephony, broadcast television, and the printed press, and instead, favour mobile and Internet based technologies, it becomes less clear how to ensure that safety-critical information is disseminated throughout the population, even though technically information dissemination has the potential to be far more effective now than in the past.

¹⁷ TCCA (TETRA + Critical Communications Association), “Mission Critical Mobile Broadband: Practical standardisation & roadmap considerations”, February 2013, <http://teworld.org/whitepaper/mission-critical-mobile-broadband-practical-standardisation-roadmap-considerations>

¹⁸ Jackson, Donny, “Global ecosystem for public-safety LTE begins to look realistic”, 11 June 2013, <http://urgentcomm.com/blog/global-ecosystem-public-safety-lte-begins-look-realistic>

¹⁹ Chandrasekhar, C. P., and Jayati Ghosh. "Information and communication technologies and health in low income countries: the potential and the constraints." *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 79.9, 2001, pp. 850-855.

²⁰ Asian Disaster Preparedness Center, Bangkok, *Managing Disasters in Asian and the Pacific. A review of Lessons Learned during the International Decade for Natural Disaster Reduction*, 1999.

Finally, the nature of communication technologies themselves needs to be reassessed. Increasingly, telecommunications systems are linked to each other. Modalities of communications become richer. The information available through these systems is changing as it is becoming richer and more commonplace. As different technologies and capabilities proliferate, the variety of available information increases, as well as the variety of technologies *through* which it becomes available. Finally, the diversity of deployed technologies is also increasing. From the user's point of view, rich, integrated, easy to use applications need to be the focal point of analysis. From a technological perspective, the multiplicity of available technological components needs to be managed and analysed, indeed with an emphasis on interoperability and functional composability. In addition, they need to retain the conceptualisation of each component's separate identity, so as to allow for alternative, interchangeable, rapidly evolving and differently regulated components enabling overall communication solutions.

The convergence of information and communication technologies means that modern communications are not only revolutionising crisis management, but the nature of the role of communication technology within crisis management is also evolving, from ad-hoc, focused services to rich, integrated services.

2.2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Communication technologies offer a variety of what, today, we might call “applications” or “services”, which we define here as the useful overall functions for users. The following list provides the critical applications that are necessary for crisis management, additional basic applications, and examples of various other possible, useful applications – see for example^{21, 22, 23, 24}.

- Critical
 - Voice (two way speech transmission, enabling users to talk to each other)
 - Text message
- Basic and important
 - Group voice communication (talk groups)
 - Voice message
 - Image transmission
 - Video transmission
 - Document transmission

²¹ Gianmarco Baldini, *Report of the workshop on Interoperable communications for Safety and Security*, Workshop jointly organised by DG ENTR and DG JRC with the support of EUROPOL and FRONTEX, Ispra, Italy, 28-29 June 2010.

²² SAFECOM, *SAFECOM Guidance on Emergency Communications Grants*, 2013. <http://www.safeocomprogram.gov>

²³ Douglas, Volney. *Operational Behaviors and Continuous Improvement*. Volney Douglas, 2010.

²⁴ Cabral Jr, James E., and Yongmin Kim. "Multimedia systems for telemedicine and their communications requirements." *Communications Magazine, IEEE*, Vol. 34, No. 7, 1996, pp. 20-27.

- Voice broadcast
- Image broadcast
- Video broadcast
- Classical Internet applications (e.g. email, file transfer)
- Web access (which potentially subsumes all the above)
- Dispatch with centralised control
- Examples of additional and specialised high-impact services/applications
 - Verification of biometric data
 - Mobile command centre
 - Wireless video surveillance and remote monitoring
 - Support for ad-hoc sensor networks deployed in the crisis area or along the border
 - Automatic number plate recognition
 - Documents scan and transmission
 - Applications for location and guiding - controls room should have the position of all the officers and vehicles in the field
 - Database access and checks
 - Monitoring of vital signs of Public Safety officers
 - Remote emergency medical services
 - Collect and share real-time operational information among Public Safety responders of various organizations
 - Access to digital maps
 - Remotely controlled devices (robots or drones)
 - Access video images of crime in progress
 - Download building plans of a burning building
 - Automatic crash notification
 - Photographs for identification of people

Functional requirements for communication technologies include “classics” such as voice and text, but also a variety of modern, “optional” but potentially very important requirements, such as video transmission, which may have a high impact in a particular scenario, such as the monitoring of vital signs of public safety officers.

2.3 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Communication technologies must also possess a variety of “qualities”, i.e. there is a range of non-functional requirements that they must satisfy. These non-functional requirements address both the active use of the technologies during a crisis, and the permanent activities of preparing, training and equipping government organisations and NGOs, as well as individual citizens, to deal with crises if they should occur. The following list provides critical and important-to-normal non-functional requirements during operation, while also providing non-functional requirements that are relevant in the preparation phase of a crisis – see for example ^{25,26,27,28}.

- Critical during operation
 - Guaranteed access (availability)
 - Reliability
 - Resiliency
 - Coverage
 - Fast communication setup
 - Off-infrastructure operation
- Important-to-normal during operation
 - Interoperability
 - QoS (Quality of Service)
 - Roaming
 - Spectrum efficiency and capacity
 - Energy efficiency (e.g. affects operational time of portable devices)
 - Usability
 - Privacy / encryption
 - Durability of hardware
 - Capability of hardware to operate in harsh environments
- During preparation
 - Costs (development, deployment, maintenance)
 - Maintainability (includes ability to detect and correct flaws in the system)
 - Training requirements in line with training capabilities for a given user population
 - Standards compliance
 - Manageability

²⁵ Douglas, 2011.

²⁶ Baldini, 2010.

²⁷ Mehta, Rutvij, Hongyuan Wang, and Lawrence Chung. "Dealing with NFRs for Smart-Phone Applications: A Goal-Oriented Approach." *Software Engineering Research, Management and Applications 2012*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012, pp. 113-125.

²⁸ SAFECOM, 2013.

Non-functional requirements for communication technologies address service quality and also management requirements such as cost and training. They also address service quality during normal operation (e.g., access and reliability) but also service quality in unusual, unplanned situations (e.g. interoperability and roaming).

2.4 COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AS PRODUCTS

One important way to classify communication technologies is as “products”. The concept of a product wraps together a (usually complicated) set of capabilities (with respect to functional and non-functional properties of the solution) as a practically usable (from the point of view of the user) and jointly analysable (from the point of view of technology and policy) unit. Of course, products are important because of their availability in practice, in contrast with the normally very large cost of developing and deploying custom solutions²⁹.

For example, a government that is preparing to deploy a nationwide emergency telecommunications infrastructure³⁰ can choose between a limited number of standards and corresponding products³¹, most prominently TETRA (primarily in the EU) and P25 (primarily in the US), even if they suffer from considerable drawbacks such as high cost and security problems. An NGO preparing to send aid to a developing country that may have experienced a natural-disaster, where telecommunications infrastructures cannot be relied upon, can choose between a limited number of standards and corresponding products, most prominently satellite solutions, e.g., INMARSAT, Iridium, Viasat, Thuraya and Globalstar, and two-way radio solutions, e.g., DMR, dPMR, and TETRA (EU), P25 (US), NXDN (commercial). Satellite connections are appropriate for global telecommunications independently of local infrastructure, while two-way radio connections are appropriate for local telecommunications primarily within pre-organised groups (i.e., for the purpose of maintaining voice contact between the aid providers) independently of local infrastructure^{32,33}.

Modern devices aim to provide additional functionalities, for example integrating satellite or two-way radio capabilities with regular GSM communications, or integrating many useful sensors, for example:

<p>“Thuraya XT-DUAL Handset The Thuraya XT Dual allows you the benefit of both regular GSM voice calling and also voice through the Thuraya satellite network. The XT Dual is one of the most rugged handsets on the market with a IP64</p>	<p>“Garmin Rino 655t Topo GPS 2-Way Radio: Rino(R) 655t. With a 5-Watt FRS/GMRS radio, 2.6" glove-friendly color touchscreen GPS with preloaded TOPO 100K maps, barometric altimeter, 3-axis compass, NOAA weather radio and 5-megapixel camera, Rino</p>
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²⁹ Panko, Raymond, and Julia Panko. *Business data networks and telecommunications*. Prentice Hall Press, 2010.

³⁰ Berioli, Matteo, Nicolas Courville, and Markus Werner. "Integrating satellite and terrestrial technologies for emergency communications: the WISECOM project." *QShine 2007 Workshop: Satellite/Terrestrial Interworking*. ACM, 2007.

³¹ Balachandran, Krishna, et al. "Mobile responder communication networks for public safety." *Communications Magazine, IEEE*, Vol. 44, No. 1, 2006, pp. 56-64.

³² Berioli, Matteo, Nicolas Courville, and Markus Werner. "Emergency communications over satellite: the WISECOM approach." *Mobile and Wireless Communications Summit, 2007. 16th IST*. IEEE, 2007.

³³ Estrem, A. Via, and Markus Werner. "Portable satellite backhauling solution for emergency communications." *Advanced satellite multimedia systems conference (asma) and the 11th signal processing for space communications workshop (spsc), 2010 5th*. IEEE, 2010.

<p>rating which means it is splash water, dust & shock proof. The handset also has a standby battery life of up to 160 hours in GSM mode. In addition to this the handset also has GPS co-ordinate tool and with one press of a button the GPS emergency helper can send a SMS to a predefined number with your co-ordinates.”³⁴</p>	<p>655t is a jack-of-all-trades. Pinpoint Your Position With its high-sensitivity GPS receiver and quad helix antenna, Rino 655t quickly finds your position and maintains it-even in heavy cover. Plus, a built-in barometric altimeter and 3-axis compass make it easy to get your bearings without the need to hold it level.”³⁵</p>
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Prospective users of these technologies can generally rely on the specifications of particular devices. Where infrastructure such as (land-line) PSTN/fiber and (mobile) GSM/3G/4G is unavailable (or when damage/congestion to such infrastructure must be planned against), backup solutions such as satellite and two-way radio can be relied upon. However, compared to mainstream commercial telecommunications solutions, these options are clearly sub-optimal due to high costs, limited availability of functions commonly offered in commercial solutions, and limited interoperability with mainstream solutions.

We should also note the potential of amateur radio to be useful for communications in the event of a crisis. Amateur radio equipment is, technically, amenable to a higher level of customisation than standardised commercial equipment. Nevertheless, from the point of view of a crisis management user, amateur radio is likely to be a solution that happens to be available on-the-spot after a crisis has occurred/begun. Amateur radio faces some significant constraints, such as requirement for a licensed (and skilled) user, and power requirements (normally a local electrical utility must be able to provide electricity, although of course a generator can be used instead if the appropriate provision has been made), while also amateur radio equipment is not *required* to be rugged and is therefore not more likely to survive a disaster than its alternatives. However, amateur radio also offers some potential benefits, such as the high level of skill and therefore capability to deal with unusual situations that the equipment’s users are required to have, normally long range communication capability, and independence from infrastructures. A link (or co-location) between an emergency command centre and a radio amateur with functioning equipment can be a valuable resource.

The following figure presents a cross reference between dominant communication technology products and the functional and non-functional requirements that have been identified in the previous sub-sections.³⁶

³⁴ GMPS Personal Communications, *Thuraya XT-DUAL Handset*, 2013. <http://www.gmpcs-us.com/Thuraya/Thuraya-XT-DUAL-Handset.htm>

³⁵ Garmin, *Rino*, no date. <http://sites.garmin.com/rino/>

³⁶ Manoj, Balakrishnan S., and Alexandra Hubenko Baker. "Communication challenges in emergency response." *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 50, No. 3, 2007, pp. 51-53.

The communication technology product categories in the figure above are discussed individually in this sub-section:

Mission-critical grade systems³⁷

- Two-way radio technically includes all systems connected through radio transmission in both directions (each terminal device can receive as well as transmit a radio signal), including for instance commercial mobile phones and amateur radio. However, these sub-categories are significant enough to be considered separately and referred to independently, so that when we refer to two-way radio we specifically address optionally but not necessarily handheld, mission-critical grade two-way radio systems. These systems are distinguished from commercial communications systems such as mobile phones, and alternative two-way radio devices which even include toys. Satellite phones are also considered as a separate category due to their distinct operational properties, although they are also radio devices that are optionally, but not necessarily handheld, bi-directional, and often built to mission-critical grade specifications.
- An important property is the full, optional or absent requirement for infrastructure. This discussion applies tangentially to satellite phones since these phones can offer dual support for satellite communications and terrestrial-infrastructure based communication. Furthermore, satellite phones are independent of *terrestrial* infrastructure, so from the point of view of such infrastructure becoming unavailable due to a crisis or disaster, it will be appropriate in some settings to consider satellite phones as infrastructure-independent.
- There are three connectivity possibilities, not mutually exclusive. The end-devices, i.e. the phones themselves, can (1) connect directly to each other, enabling communication without any reliance on infrastructure, or (2) connect to a repeater or base station, which can be permanent infrastructure or simply an additional item of mobile equipment, or (3) connect in a trunked mode in which a central infrastructure supports the communication, providing repeater or base station support and also managing the devices by e.g. making centralised allocations of channels to calls.

TWO-WAY RADIO (ANALOGUE)

- Analogue two-way radio might be thought of as an almost obsolete technology, however it continues to offer some advantages: it is low-cost, simple to use and highly reliable. When the capability of off-infrastructure operation is required, while a data connection is not required, these advantages may motivate its selection.
- Analogue two-way radio is restricted to supporting voice communication. It cannot provide modern digital applications, digital encryption or interoperate with commercial digital telecommunication technologies.

TWO-WAY RADIO (DIGITAL)

- Digital two-way radio was developed as an upgrade to analogue two-way radio, in parallel to the transition of commercial mobile telephony from analogue to digital (1G to 2G and beyond). Although the most popular systems (e.g. TETRA, P25, dPMR, NXDN) offer trunked operation, the capability of off-infrastructure operation remains one of their key advantages. As these systems are designed to offer high performance,

³⁷ Erwin, Carl Kent, and David Aylward. "Next Generation Interorganizational Emergency Communications: Making Tangible Progress While Broader Efforts Continue." *Aspen Institute*, 2006.

good Quality of Service (QoS), reliability, durability, as well as digital encryption, etc. can be expected.

- Modern implementation of digital two-way radio offer smartphone-like capabilities, thus supporting many basic requirements such as image transmission and web access, and can potentially support emerging applications such as verifying biometric data as well. A key concern to large-scale planning is the improved spectrum efficiency of digital two-way radio compared to analogue two-way radio, which is critical for equipping a large group in a given area (e.g., police force in a city) but will be irrelevant in remote areas (e.g., humanitarian mission in an area where telecommunication infrastructure has been destroyed). On the other hand, the cost of such systems is generally very high.

SATELLITE PHONE (ANALOGUE) and SATELLITE PHONE (DIGITAL)

- Satellite phone is the second primary alternative when off-infrastructure operation is required. This technology can offer extremely good coverage, and high-quality implementations are available that are reliable and easy to use. Call set-up time may be worse compared to two-way radio, energy efficiency needs to be considered (the key parameter being how long a handheld phone can be used with a given battery), and the quality of service under the expected weather conditions should be checked. Spectrum efficiency is a problem with satellite telecommunications, making this an expensive technology³⁸.
- Satellite phones can also offer data communications, so they support a multitude of functional requirements similarly to digital two-way radio and smartphones. However, this service can be extremely expensive.

AMATEUR RADIO³⁹

- Amateur radio involves radio communications between licensed users for strictly recreational and non-commercial purposes. A group (or individual) equipping themselves for a crisis (for instance, the fire department in an urban environment, or a humanitarian mission to a remote location) would not face a choice, in advance, of deploying amateur radio or not. However, amateur radio can operate independently of infrastructures; if infrastructures are damaged or otherwise inoperable during a crisis, turning to amateur radio can give crisis responders a new communication option. Thus, maintaining contacts with amateur radio operators would be a useful preparation, and in the case of a crisis the amateur radio operators could be called in to help if their equipment remained operable.
- Additional advantages of amateur radio are that it often achieves long-range communication, and the operator can tune the equipment on the spot to achieve acceptable quality of service in a highly adverse environment.
- Beyond this, amateur radio suffers from many limitations, such as low usability and high training requirements to operate. Finally, data services are not supported.

³⁸ Ilcev, Stojce D. "Global Mobile Satellite Communications: For Maritime, Land and Aeronautical Applications." *Global Mobile Satellite Communications: For Maritime, Land and Aeronautical Applications*, by SD Ilcev. 2005 XXIV, 496 p. 1-4020-7767-X. Berlin: Springer, 2005

³⁹ ITU, 2005.

Commercial broadcasting

Commercial broadcasting is primarily used for its ability to provide one-way communication (although digital television may achieve a departure from this constraint). The party involved in responding to and managing a crisis can convey information to a broad audience, if access to the broadcaster is possible. The regular terminal equipment (radios, televisions) is deployed on the side of the audience.

BROADCAST RADIO

- Broadcast radio refers to the standard radio services. Broadcast radio is restricted to voice broadcasting. The use of broadcast radio is widespread, i.e. reaching a very broad audience. It is thus an excellent way to achieve broad dissemination of critical information to an audience.

ANALOGUE TELEVISION

- Analogue television refers to the standard television services, but specifically to the analogue technology that has been phased out in most developed countries. Analogue television offers audio-visual broadcasting capabilities, and is widely used. It is thus an excellent way to achieve broad dissemination of critical information to an audience.

DIGITAL TELEVISION (AS EVOLVING)

- Digital television refers to the standard television services, but specifically to the digital technology that has been relatively recently introduced in most developed countries. Digital television offers the same advantages as analogue television, i.e. reaching a broad audience, with audio-visual information. In addition, digital television is constantly evolving to incorporate more data services, and potentially in the near future full Web access will be possible.

LAND-LINE TELEPHONE

- Land-line telephone refers to the standard, wired telephone services, mainly PSTN (analogue) and ISDN (digital). Land-lines are a relatively old technology and offer only point-to-point and, with additional services, group and messaging voice communication, and only to users of fixed telephones. On the other hand, as a technology that has been optimised over many years, it offers high performance with respect to practically all non-functional requirements except digital encryption.

WEB (INTERNET/WEBSITE)

- Web access is worth identifying as a communications service independently of specific telecommunications infrastructure, since it is enabled by many different such infrastructures (from satellite to mobile to ADSL). Web access enables a broad variety of services and applications, as it is effectively a general-purpose platform where virtually any application can be implemented. As users can access the web through a variety of devices and services, it offers high interoperability, and roaming. Digital encryption is also available.

Commercial mobile (cellular) communications⁴⁰

- Consumer-level mobile telephony has seen an explosive growth in recent years. Vast demand and equivalent supply have driven down prices⁴¹. The underlying infrastructure

⁴⁰ Gibson, Jerry D., ed. *Mobile communications handbook*. Vol. 45. CRC press, 2012.

is very expensive, thus serious investment has been made in ensuring its safety from damage and overall reliability. Especially in the form of the smartphone, mobile telephony has enabled access to the Internet, also providing very powerful devices that are capable of supporting a vast array of applications. The advantages of mobile telephony include high interoperability. As a ubiquitous consumer service, it is accessible by all, whereas specialist services and devices are often not interoperable. Similarly, roaming works for mobile telephony but not necessarily for specialist services.

- However, expensive infrastructure is relied upon. If this infrastructure is destroyed, service halts. In areas where such infrastructure does not exist, the service is not available – this constraint does not only include e.g., remote regions in developing countries, but even rural areas, forests, mountainous regions. Also, during a crisis, local congestion becomes a major issue: many calls originating from the immediate vicinity of a disaster can easily overwhelm the local infrastructure.

SMART PHONES and 3G+

- Smartphones are almost mobile computers, capable of a vast array of powerful applications, and with fast data connectivity when subscribed to a 3G or beyond service. The main drawback that should be kept in mind is very poor battery life. In the example of citizens stranded due to a disaster (e.g., under wreckage after an earthquake or in a flooded area) they may lose their connection due to their device's battery running out.

FEATURE PHONES and 2.5G+

- A typical combination is a weaker device and service than the previous case – a feature phone and a 2.5G or 2.75G connection. This combination is interesting because it is the entry-level technology for mobile Internet and web access. Although not as impressive as smartphones 3G+, the current combination should be able to support web access, and through this a reasonable variety of useful services. Such technology may well be the prevalent available option, depending on the region of the world under consideration.

GSM/CELL PHONES and 2G

- This is digital telephony without a data connection, except if relying on a solution such as WAP, which is very low-performance. Nevertheless, as a digital service, GSM will enable some additional digital services, such as transmitting text messages and images.

ANALOGUE WIRELESS PHONES (1G)

- This obsolete technology allows only analogue voice communication.

The “classical” way to understand ICTs is as products – e.g. a mobile, allowing voice communications on the go in areas with terrestrial infrastructure, or a satellite phone and service allowing voice and data communications anywhere in the world. In this section, partners have identified the main categories of such products, and tabulated and discussed their main properties.

2.5 SENSORS DEPLOYED IN COMMUNICATIONS DEVICES

⁴¹ See for example strategyanalytics blog, “HTC, Apple & Samsung Top Smartphone Retail Price Decline Comparison”, 27 September 2012, <http://blogs.strategyanalytics.com/PRT/post/2012/09/27/HTC-Apple-Samsung-Top-Smartphone-Retail-Price-Decline-Comparison.aspx>

Modern ICT enables communication in multiple modalities. In our discussion of communication technologies as products (above), we referred to voice communications, but also the transmission of images, video, and text. Measurements can be made by a wide variety of wearable or other sensors, and transmitted over a data connection – for example, the command centre can monitor biometrics of first responders. Here, partners have identified a number of categories of relevant sensors (see for example the specifications of current market leaders in the smartphone market^{42,43}):

- Widely available
 - fundamental
 - microphone
 - important
 - picture camera
 - video camera
 - GPS
 - compass
 - additional
 - altimeter
 - barometer
 - hygrometer
 - thermometer
 - gyroscope
 - accelerometer
 - magnetometer
- Emerging
 - full set of biometric sensors
 - infrared camera
 - distance measurement
 - 3D camera
 - air quality sensors, e.g. CO2 sensors

An important emerging property of populations of connected smart devices such as smartphones is that their sensor readings can be aggregated.⁴⁴ For example, the reading of a single device's atmospheric pressure sensor may not offer enough information to provide an

⁴² Apple, "Iphone", 2013. <http://www.apple.com/iphone/specs.html>

⁴³ Samsung, "Samsung Galaxy S4", 2013. <http://www.samsung.com/uk/consumer/mobile-devices/smartphones/android/GT-I9505ZWABTU-spec>

⁴⁴ Agarwal, Vikas, et al. "USense--A Smartphone Middleware for Community Sensing." *Mobile Data Management (MDM), 2013 IEEE 14th International Conference*, Vol. 1, 2013.

improvement on centralised weather forecasts, but the readings of thousands or even millions of such sensors, and other, related ones, may well be sufficient to do so. A second example includes; the measurement of temperature at currently-safe locations in a burning building could reveal information about the fire, e.g., its propagation patterns. This discussion is relevant to the organisation and planning of the long-term deployment of mobile devices, because applications exploiting sensor capabilities are likely to emerge during the lifetime of the deployment. Accordingly, stakeholders should evaluate investing in sensor capabilities even if they are not immediately exploited by existing applications.

In reality, with fast data connections and a plethora of sensors available, it is no longer necessary to distinguish communication services fundamentally based on the sensor type used. Previously, communications using the microphone corresponded to a voice service, communications using the keyboard corresponded to a text service, communications using the video camera corresponded to a videophone service, etc. However, we now have data connectivity on the one hand (which can be provided by any relevant infrastructure or a point-to-point communication capability), and any number of communication services that can be offered using the appropriate sensors each time, as illustrated by the examples above.

Multiple sensors on mobile devices – including microphone and camera, but also GPS or even CO2 sensors – enable the communication of rich information, supporting valuable current and emerging services.

2.6 COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AS APPLICATIONS

The industrial development of specialised communications solutions for crisis management involves integrating custom end-to-end technologies for a complete communication capability. These technologies must be standardised with the intent of achieving mission-critical grade qualities as discussed above, it is becoming increasingly apparent that there is a key flaw in this approach: technology is simply evolving too fast for this approach to remain competitive. While this approach does still provide the most reliable solutions for certain critically important key services, e.g., mission-critical voice communications, it cannot be employed as the sole strategy for the ongoing development of technologies for communication in the context of crisis management. In this section, we consider the development of new technologies, and outline a framework for assessing, in general, new technologies for communication in crisis management. In contrast, in the previous section, we discussed existing technologies that can be used as-is in a practical deployment addressing an ongoing crisis, or creating immediate preparedness for crises. In that scenario, the issue was relatively straightforward in that the specific requirements of a given deployment can be analysed and matched against the capabilities of currently mature technologies.

At this point, therefore, we can ask a deeper ontological question: What is a communication technology for crisis management? In the era of “hand-held analogue radio transceivers” a technical end-to-end definition of a specific radio solution might be a useful definition: a device with certain specifications produces a given modulation of a human voice, transmits this signal over an appropriate transmission medium, and so on, until the receiver hears the reproduction of the same voice – this could be defined as one, particular communication technology, which can be compared to an alternative one, i.e., a particular device and its design could be used to define a particular communication technology.

It is interesting to consider an example of recent communication mechanisms, which demonstrate why it is hard to equate a particular communication solution to a useful overall category of communication technology^{45,46}.

- People affected by a natural disaster may use Twitter to ask for help and receive updates on the situation around them.
 - Twitter can be used from a broad variety of devices / networking, including:
 - Desktop computer connected using a land line (e.g. DSL)
 - Mobile phone using a custom app and connected to mobile Internet (e.g. 2G+WAP/2.5G/2.75G/3G/LTE)
 - Mobile phone using just SMS (e.g. with a GSM connection)
 - However, Twitter imposes a limit on the number of tweets that one account can transmit per day. Twitter accounts used to broadcast critical information to people can run into this limit. Also, misinformation on Twitter is not, in general, centrally controlled – and, authentication of the real identity of the owner of a new account is not enforced. The question of governance arises in these cases.
 - Twitter is basically text based, but other media can be linked to it (e.g., use of images).

We can see here that a medium is being used (text) that can be technically supported to incorporate other media as well (e.g. images). As soon as the technology is capable of such an extension, via a commercially controlled service (which can find itself in need of providing governance corresponding to life-critical situations), using communication channels in a truly “scavenging” manner (if a channel is capable of transferring the required data, it can quickly be integrated into the ecosystem), and where hardware and infrastructure requirements can vary wildly (e.g. we could ask: do we need a battery to use Twitter? Do we need mains power? The answer of course depends not on Twitter as a “medium” for communication, but on the specific technology being used to access Twitter)^{47,48}.

We can easily translate the concerns of this example of a broadly popular system to specialised applications. For instance, when a firefighter can download the building plans of a burning building to his/her mobile device as he/she drives towards the site of the crisis, basically all of the underlying technology becomes irrelevant, as long as it provides the required functionality. The plans could be scanned from paper records or drawn from a crisis management database, transmitted via MMS from the phone of one firefighter to the phone of another or accessed by the receiving firefighter using a dedicated and optimised mobile app, the communication mechanism (independently of the user interface) could be anything from MMS to 3G/LTE or a custom and specialised national security broadband network, and of course the device could be a smartphone or tablet or in-car computer or any other appropriate device. Once more, in this case, which is “the” communication technology?

⁴⁵ Mills, Alexander, et al. "Web 2.0 emergency applications: how useful can twitter be for emergency response." *Journal of Information Privacy & Security*, Vol. 5, No. 3, 2009, pp. 3-26.

⁴⁶ Hughes, Amanda Lee, and Leysia Palen. "Twitter adoption and use in mass convergence and emergency events." *International Journal of Emergency Management*, Vol. 5, No. 3, 2009, pp. 248-260.

⁴⁷ Kumar, Shamanth, et al. "TweetTracker: An Analysis Tool for Humanitarian and Disaster Relief." *ICWSM*. 2011.

⁴⁸ Hossmann, Theus, et al. "Twitter in disaster mode: Security architecture." *Proceedings of the Special Workshop on Internet and Disasters*. ACM, 2011.

This discussion is important for planning the deployment of ICTs for crisis management, and for assessing opportunities to develop new ICTs for crisis management. It is clear that communication technologies in crisis management are:

- From the point of view of their users:
 - Application-oriented (better than the older paradigm of product-oriented)
 - This also covers “traditional” services, such as voice communication
- From the point of view of the technology itself:
 - Component-oriented
 - Applications can be built by integrating the appropriate components, e.g. for networking, display, data access, etc., and often alternative components can be available at the same time, offering redundancy and therefore increased availability and reliability

In the next section, we consider how we can technically organise the consideration of these points.

This section has argued conceptually that a shift is necessary, from viewing communication technologies as products, to breaking them down into capabilities, which can be used to compose a variety of valuable services or applications.

2.7 COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

This section provides additional technical argumentation to support the reasoning of the previous section.⁴⁹

It is an instructive exercise to reinterpret the common logic behind various mainstream (and often mutually incompatible) protocol stacks from the point of view of determining capabilities and features of communications systems in the context of crisis management. We should consider the detailed OSI abstract networking model as well as the dominant TCP/IP, but for example we can also consider SS7 (“Signalling System No. 7”) and WAP (“Wireless Application Protocol”).

The following diagrams address the OSI, SS7 and WAP architectures⁵⁰. We can see the example of the different possible conceptualisations of the role of SMS by comparing these models. In the SS7 model, SMS is based on MAP, which is an application-layer protocol. This is reasonable: SMS is a communication service offered directly to end-users, so it should be placed at the top layer. Nevertheless, the WAP model places SMS in the Network layer (under “bearers” in the figure). This usage by WAP is “archaic”⁵¹: before 2.5G wireless telephony (i.e., before GPRS), WAP was basically able to “hack” SMS to deliver data over a network basically designed for voice communications. However, before we dismiss the WAP

⁴⁹ Readers with a non-technical background may wish to skip this section.

⁵⁰ Tanenbaum, Andrew S., and David J. Wetherall. *Computer networks*. Pearson Higher Ed, 2012.

⁵¹ Edwards, James, and Richard Bramante. *Networking Self-Teaching Guide: OSI, TCP/IP, LAN's, MAN's, WAN's, Implementation, Management, and Maintenance*. Wiley.com, 2009.

example as an unrepresentative, temporary, poorly engineered solution, we can remember the example used above that led to the current discussion, i.e., of Twitter also using SMS at the level of networking.

Figure 2: OSI Model⁵²

Figure 3: Two slightly different SS7 protocol stacks^{53, 54}

⁵² <http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/d/d3/Osi-model-jb.png>

⁵³ Cisco Systems, “Cisco documentation: SS7 Protocol Stack”, 2002. http://docstore.mik.ua/univercd/cc/td/doc/product/tel_pswt/vco_prod/ss7_fund/ss7fun03.htm

⁵⁴ GL Communications Inc, “Scripted Mtp2 Simulator”, no date. <http://www.gl.com/wcs-mtp2-simulator.html>

Figure 4: WAP model and protocol stack⁵⁵

These examples demonstrate that it is useful to break down our consideration of communication technologies according to an abstract model similar to the OSI model. Rather than discussing the capabilities of an “atomic” “communication technology”, we can discuss the capabilities of different tools (protocols, implementations of protocols, hardware devices, or others) to perform the services expected at each level considered. Of course, only in relatively rare cases, such as the SMS example, will a single tool be able to be considered as offering different capabilities depending on within which layer we employ it. Most tools will be designed and implemented to function within a specific layer, according to the rationale of that layer. Nevertheless, the main point is that we can compose services using different solutions at the various necessary layers⁵⁶.

For instance, how might Twitter offer redundancy in order to ensure its service can be used as a mission-critical grade service? Building on the above discussion, we might suggest that the transport layer (theoretically) or the application layer (practically, because that is the infrastructure that a user application such as Twitter will actually interface with) should be aware of the capability to transmit using either SMS or a 3G data connection, and for the purpose of redundancy could be extended with the capability to use both in combination.

This contrasts with the approaches of solutions such as TETRA, P25 or MPT-1327, which define their own, custom protocol stacks. Instead of such an approach, we recommend a “networking layers as a service” approach. A commercial adoption of such an approach would allow consumer grade solutions to employ simpler tools at each layer in order to build more economical products. For mission-critical grade solutions, improved performance at each layer may be achievable through very different means, therefore optimising separately at each layer will be a highly optimising strategy. For example, at some layer a commercial provider may simply be able to offer an SLA (service level agreement) guaranteeing a higher level of QoS (quality of service) in order to reach mission-critical grade quality, whereas at another layer a custom solution may need to be designed from the ground up.

⁵⁵ Hstelnet, “WAP (Wireless Application Protocol)”, no date. <http://www.hstelnet.com/english/data/info.html>

⁵⁶ Garzia, F. *Handbook of Communications Security*. WIT Press, 2013.

The discussion above has indicated how technology development can progress beyond the currently available solutions. In order to also make this discussion relevant to assessing currently available solutions, we can think from the focused point of view of Communication Technologies for Crisis Management and define high-level, conceptual abstractions of layers according to which a telecommunications solution can be assessed. A good solution will be one that is judged sufficient with respect to all of these layers.

Physical link

- Here we should assess features that are relevant for NFRs, and depend on transmission media that are employed, e.g., wired connections including copper or optical, and wireless connections at a variety of frequency bands with very different properties, as well as depending on different infrastructures that may be used to implement the physical link, e.g. satellite, base stations, or no infrastructure (for some use cases, capability to operate without any infrastructure is a critical requirement).
 - The user's experience will be directly affected by some performance aspects of the technology, for instance whether line of sight is required for the connection, or whether power at a nationwide level during a natural disaster is required for the infrastructure; other important aspects of the connection include its range and the relationship between its performance and factors such as the terrain and weather.

Networking

- Here we should assess features that are relevant for functional as well as NFRs, depending on the networking solution that is employed, e.g. including not only aspects of the networking protocols used but also features of potential providers of networking services.
 - Performance aspects of the technology will manifest usually as QoS features or even as factors affecting availability, for example call setup time is a critical issue for the time-sensitive environment of first responders, while another issue is vulnerability of the networking service (for example a trunking system may be vulnerable to the destruction of central infrastructure, while a commercial infrastructure may in fact be more extensive and therefore more resilient to physical infrastructure damage, but susceptible to congestion during a crisis).

Applications

- Here we should assess the functional offerings that users can employ in the pursuit of crisis management; for instance, the simple and fundamental applications listed above such as voice and text communications, and the specialised applications also given above such as remote emergency medical services or remote access to buildings' plans.
 - The exact features of applications should be considered, for example voice communication includes point-to-point voice communication, group voice communication and broadcast voice communication; of course the chosen application features will heavily influence which of the features at the lower layers are relevant, and how they should be assessed (for example, if group voice communication is required, commercial mobile telephony may not offer this feature; in the case of off-infrastructure communication, if very-long-range communication is required, a satellite link may be the best option); for more advanced applications, there are many more issues that need to be considered

in a technology assessment, such as data access, authentication, and compatibility of presentation technologies.

This section has argued technically for the same point as the previous section – that a shift is necessary, from viewing communication technologies as products, to breaking them down into capabilities, which can be used to compose a variety of valuable services or applications.

2.8 INTEROPERABILITY OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

A key technological and policy issue is interoperability between communication technologies^{57,58}. Different government organizations, NGOs, citizens, or a combinations of these actors, may have operational communication technologies in place enabling the between a subset of these groups, but may find it impossible to communicate with the remainder of these groups.⁵⁹

It is important to stress that policy is also a determining factor in compatibility issues. For example, different groups each using their own encryption and without prior coordination to enable cross-group communication will find themselves unable to interoperate, even if technically the devices being used are interoperable. A more fundamental issue is the overall compatibility of solutions chosen by different groups, since each could employ an utterly different solution. For example, government first responders employing a mission-critical grade but specialised telecommunications solution may not be able to use it to communicate with citizens using standard commercial communication devices.

As mentioned in the discussion above, interoperability issues can arise due to incompatibilities at various architectural layers⁶⁰; such interoperability issues are indicative of a variety of potential problems. For instance, solutions technically capable of being fully interoperable may be used without preparation for shared encryption policy between different groups of users, rendering communication impossible. A more common example is the use of different frequency bands for various radio solutions – for instance, two-way radio bands in the EU and the US are allocated differently, and equipment intended for these different regions may be incompatible.

A related aspect is roaming – will the communications solution used by an individual or group continue to function if they find themselves outside their normal field of operation?

Another interoperability issue is directly relevant to social networking as a component of communication technologies. Namely, social networking sites are notorious for shunning interoperability. For example, a data mining application correlating data between multiple

⁵⁷ Gaynor, Mark, et al. "Open infrastructure for a nationwide emergency services network." *Crisis Response and Management and Emerging Information Systems: Critical Applications*, 2011, p. 96.

⁵⁸ Mayer-Schönberger, Viktor. "Emergency communications: the quest for interoperability in the United States and Europe", 2002.

⁵⁹ Pechta, Laura E., Dale C. Brandenburg, and Matthew W. Seeger. "Understanding the dynamics of emergency communication: propositions for a four-channel model." *Journal of Homeland Security and Emergency Management*, Vol. 7, No. 1., 2010.

⁶⁰ Gaynor et al., 2011.

Social Networking Sites in order to discover the needs of citizens facing a crisis will likely be hindered by the “wall gardens” being erected by many Social Networking Sites.

When multiple individuals or organisations that have been separately organised, or come from different areas, collaborate during a crisis, interoperability and roaming capabilities are critical, without these properties, communications between individuals or groups may be found to be extremely difficult, if not near impossible.

2.9 CASE STUDIES OF RECENT TRENDS IN NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS

As will be further discussed in Chapter 3, communication technologies play an integral role in many aspects of crisis management. In this sub-section we briefly mention some specific case studies that demonstrate some interesting developments.

- Social networking sites: towards replacing news channels⁶¹
 - “[In the case of] Hurricane Sandy ... millions of Americans looked to resources including Twitter and Facebook to keep informed, locate loved ones, notify authorities and express support. Gone are the days of one-way communication where only official sources provide bulletins on disaster news.”
 - “Following the Boston Marathon bombings, one quarter of Americans reportedly looked to Facebook, Twitter and other social networking sites for information, according to The Pew Research Center. The sites also formed a key part of the information cycle.”
- Social networking sites played a large role in the response to the 2010 earthquake and resulting crisis in Haiti – particularly Twitter⁶²
 - “As the 2010 Haiti crisis revealed, the usefulness of new forms of information gathering is limited by the awareness of responders that new data sources exist.”
 - “ ‘Generally we’ve gotten information...on TV and radio, but some people do not always have access to that. But just about every Haitian has a mobile phone.’ “
 - “In Haiti, one of the most studied emergencies in recent history, it has proven impossible to accurately count the number of NGOs operating there. Estimates range from 3,000 to 20,000.”
 - “A July 2012 study demonstrated that real-time monitoring of Twitter messages in Haiti could have predicted the October/November 2010 cholera outbreaks two weeks earlier than they were detected.”
- Unexpected resources can play a useful role; old or simple technologies (such as amateur radio) can prove reliable, with critical value during a crisis⁶³
 - “...when he [the Operations Manager at the ... Fire Department - Communications Division] arrived at the center [the emergency management center] it ‘had very limited communications, with no land line phone service, no Internet, spotty cell coverage, and limited radio communications...’ [He] assessed the equipment in the center and set up a workstation. He requested that the amateur radio operator return to the regional coordination center to

⁶¹ Maron, Dina, “How Social Media Is Changing Disaster Response”, *Scientific American*, 7 Jun3 2013. <http://www.scientificamerican.com/article.cfm?id=how-social-media-is-changing-disaster-response>

⁶² OCHA, 2013.

⁶³ OEC, *Emergency Communications Case Study: Hurricane Irene-North Carolina*, April 2012. www.dhs.gov

provide a direct communications link to the State Emergency Operation Center (EOC) via amateur radio. ... When the local amateur radio operator arrived, he initiated three radio nets on three different frequency bands, and was directed to make contact with as many county emergency operation centers as possible. ... they found that while ‘a few PSAPs (public safety answering points) had been flooded, were running on generator power, or moved to a backup center, a majority of PSAPs and EOCs were fully functional with no problems’.”

Case studies illustrate the value of communication technologies for crisis management, and also illustrate the evolving patterns of use of these technologies.

2.10 STATISTICS ON THE ADOPTION OF DIGITAL COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

The following charts⁶⁴ show key statistics concerning the penetration of digital communication technologies in various regions of the world. It is clear that digital communication technologies are important and prevalent; however, these statistics demonstrate also that digital communication technologies are rapidly reaching the point where they are fully inclusive, offering not just extensive but also almost complete availability to all citizens in the world except for truly extreme cases. Hence, it is worth pursuing research and development efforts towards solutions that optimise the use of these technologies, rather than older generations of communication technology, for the purposes of crisis management.

One key observation that should be emphasized is that the developing world is rapidly adopting mobile digital telecommunications, in many cases skipping the step of wired broadband connections completely. Nevertheless, Internet access using one access technology or another is on trajectory to achieve complete coverage within a space of years (as opposed to decades), with a key milestone that can be expected to mark the truly near approach to complete coverage being the provision of Internet access through all mobile telephony subscriptions, as obsolete technologies such as pure GSM are replaced globally by at least 2.5G services and Internet-capable terminal devices.

Indeed, even in the EU and the US, mobile has overtaken broadband as a communications tool in terms of penetration. We see broadband peaking at under 30% for the European Union, while mobile telephone penetration is much higher: even in sub-Saharan Africa, it is over 50%. Internet users and mobile telephony penetration are highly correlated even though not all mobile telephony offers Internet access. Thus, the two most important factors in Internet access reaching true ubiquity will be the further increase of mobile telephony penetration and standardisation of Internet access as a feature of all mobile telephony services (for example, in south Asia we have 70% mobile telephony penetration, 10% Internet users).

⁶⁴ All data from EUROSTAT and WHO through <http://www.google.com/publicdata>

Broadband penetration rate

Figure 5: Broadband penetration rate – worldwide, 2011

Figure 6: Fixed broadband Internet subscriptions against mobile cellular subscriptions per 100 people – worldwide, 2011

Figure 7: Internet users as percentage of population against mobile cellular subscriptions per 100 people – worldwide, 2011

Figure 8: Internet users as percentage of population against mobile cellular subscriptions per 100 people – worldwide, broken down into individual countries, 2011

Communication technology availability is approaching ubiquity throughout the world, even in poorer regions. Mobile telephones are contributing significantly to this trend. Nevertheless, emergency planners should examine communications infrastructure availability in their region of interest.

2.11 CONCLUSION

Communication technologies are having a major impact on crisis management. Already mobile communications and data communications are enabling much more effective crisis management in many cases. We have discussed the desirable properties of communication technologies for crisis management. We have argued that a framework for assessing technologies for crisis management should consider these technologies as providing useful components, which can be composed in multiple ways in order to provide valuable services and applications. Indeed, it becomes worthwhile to invest in deploying hardware capabilities for which no operational applications exist yet, because applications are emerging which constantly offer the prospect of revolutionising crisis management – for example, investing in devices with varied and powerful sensors should always be positively considered.

3 STATE OF THE ART OF NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Crisis communication is not restricted to information communication technologies, but as briefly mentioned in Chapter 2, is now supplemented by the development and widespread use of new media applications.⁶⁵

The planet has gone online, producing and sharing vast quantities of information. OCHA, 2012, p. 2.

These new media applications provide visual information as well as the ability to enable users to interact and share information with other users. These applications range from social networking websites to tailor-made crisis management tools and applications. Combined, these tools provide various stakeholders with the opportunity to co-ordinate and collaborate to respond to an emerging crises, as well as preparing for future crises. Accordingly, the aim of this chapter is to provide a baseline analysis of the various new media applications available to assist with crisis management.

To provide some context of the application market, partners conducted a simple search of applications via two application stores; Apple’s App Store and Google Play. The following table summarises the results of the search:

Table 1: Applications available to smart phone users

Store	Term	Number of applications
Apple Store - iPhone	Disaster	389
Apple Store - iPad	Disaster	269
Apple Store – iPhone	Emergency	2,057
Apple Store – iPad	Emergency	772
Google Play (Android)	Disaster	48
Google Play (Android)	Emergency	48

*Search was conducted on: 26 July 2013

Whilst the keyword search using the words “disaster” and “emergency” seems to turn up a large number of applications, not all applications are relevant to responding to crises. For instance, some of the applications included in the results included games and radio tracking devices. Thus, it is necessary for this chapter to focus on those applications and other web-based tools that are currently recognised as being useful for responding to crises. Accordingly, partners have examined a series of incident related journal articles, news articles and trade magazine articles to identify new media tools that are being used to respond to different types of crises.

What follows is a baseline identification of new media applications. Partners will provide more detailed information relating to the use of social media in crisis situations in D2.2 “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations” of the COSMIC project.

⁶⁵ For further clarification between the telecommunications and new media please see Chapter 1 of this report.

3.1 SUMMARY OF NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS FOR CRISIS MANAGEMENT

In order to conduct a baseline analysis of new media applications utilised in crisis management, partners have sought to identify and describe different applications based on the following criteria:

Figure 9: Classification of new media applications

It is important to note that many of the new media applications discussed in this chapter can be accessed using a variety of means. However for analysis purposes, partners have identified tools according to their primary function; that is what they were originally designed for prior to the diffusion of mobile applications across devices.

The following table provides a summary of the new media applications that partners have identified and discussed in this chapter:

Table 2: New media applications for crisis management

Name	Primary application	Functions	How accessed	Key dates
Twitter	Social networking	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Request and offer assistance /Relay /Campaign /Organise	SMS/Mobile/ Web	Launched globally - March 2007
Facebook	Social networking	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Request and offer assistance /Relay /Campaign /Organise	SMS/Mobile/ Web	Launched globally - September 2006
Google+	Social networking	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Request and offer assistance /Relay /Campaign /Organise	Mobile/Web	June 2011
YouTube	Social networking	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Campaign	Mobile/Web	February 2005

Reddit	Social networking	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Request and offer assistance /Relay /Campaign /Organise	Mobile/Web	June 2005
Blog	Social networking	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Request and offer assistance /Relay /Campaign /Organise	Mobile/Web	1999+
Google public alerts	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Google person finder	Crowdsourcing	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Custom Google maps	Crowdsourcing	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Google earth	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Google fusion tables	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Google docs and spreadsheets	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Google sites	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)
Airbnb	Web tool	Request and offer assistance/ Organise	Mobile/Web	October 2012 (Hurricane Sandy)
AMBER alert Europe	Crowdsourcing	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Relay	SMS/Mobile/ Web	March 2013
European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	<i>Unknown</i>
Natuurbrandgevaar	Web tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	<i>Unknown</i>
Ushahidi	Crowdsourcing	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Organise	Mobile/Web/ SMS	2008
Ubalert	Web tool	One-way communication/Two-way communication/Relay/Organise	Mobile/Web	August 2011
Hurricane by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/ Organise/ Campaign	Mobile	July 2012

Tornado by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/ Organise/ Campaign	Mobile	February 2013
Wildfire by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/ Organise/ Campaign	Mobile	January 2013
Earthquake by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/ Organise/ Campaign	Mobile	September 2012
American Red Cross: Shelter View	Mobile tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile	February 2011
First Aid App by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile	<i>Unknown</i>
Disaster Alert	Mobile tool	One-way communication/ Relay/Organise	Mobile	July 2010
Earthquake	Mobile tool	One-way communication/Relay/Organise	Mobile	June 2010
NL-alert	Mobile tool	One-way communication/ Organise	SMS	<i>Unknown</i>
Red panic button	Mobile tool	One-way communication/Request assistance	Mobile	March 2011
Tsunami early warning	Mobile tool	One-way communication/ Organise	SMS/Mobile	December 2011
Waze	Mobile tool	One-way communication/ Organise	Mobile/Web	2008

3.2 SOCIAL NETWORKING WEBSITES

Social network sites are “web-based services that allow individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system”⁶⁶.

Social network sites differ in their function, makeup and size, with some set up with a particular purpose and goal in mind—such as the fostering of business relationships (e.g. LinkedIn, Xing), sharing of photographs (Flickr), forming specialized communities (Academia.edu) and others, like Facebook, Twitter, MySpace, having no specifically expressed function other than facilitating social connectivity. There are also social network sites that are used by citizens in specific geographic regions, for instance; the use of Sina Weibo in China and Intafeen in the Middle East and North Africa.⁶⁷

⁶⁶ Boyd, D.M., and N.B. Ellison, “Social Network Sites: Definition, History, and Scholarship”, *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, Vol. 38, No. 3, 2010, article 11.
<http://jcmc.indiana.edu/vol13/issue1/boyd.ellison.html>

⁶⁷ This report does not include an explanation of all social networking websites; just those mainstream sites that appear to have been used in disaster response. For a comprehensive list of social networking websites visit:
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_social_networking_websites

In Europe, as depicted in the figure below, the number of social networking website users is widespread, with those in the Netherlands, the UK and Sweden being the most active users. Those in Romania and the Czech Republic appear to use social networking sites less often.⁶⁸

Figure 10: ONS and Eurostat, 2013.

3.2.1 Twitter

Twitter was originally a privately-funded organisation which started as a side project in March 2006 by Jack Dorsey. Fully established in May 2007, Twitter is now a real-time, short messaging service that functions over “multiple networks and devices”. A tweet, a form of micro blogging, is comprised of no more than 140 characters and can be uploaded via instant messaging services, the World Wide Web and mobile phone technology.⁶⁹

Twitter has seen widespread adoption throughout the globe, with estimates of 500 million users in March 2013. On average, there are approximately 500 million tweets published per day. Those accessing Twitter need not actively use the service themselves, instead, an estimated 40% of users access Twitter and use it as a “curated news feed of updates that reflect their passions”.⁷⁰

The use of Twitter in crisis response has been widely adopted.⁷¹ Twitter has several functions that can be optimised to respond to a crisis:

- One-way and two-way communication: With the use of a dedicated hashtag (#) and direct messages, Twitter helps to facilitate discussion between stakeholders. Due to its unique ability to enable individuals and groups to follow one another without the requirement of an existing relationship, Twitter enables those that are not immediately

⁶⁸ “Social Networking: The UK as a Leader in Europe”, 13 June 2013.

<http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/rdit2/Internet-access---households-and-individuals/social-networking--the-uk-as-a-leader-in-europe/sty-social-networking-2012.html>

⁶⁹ Twitter, *Twitter: About*, 2013. <https://twitter.com/about>

⁷⁰ Holt, Richard, “Twitter in Numbers”, *Telegraph.co.uk*, 21 March 2013.

<http://www.telegraph.co.uk/technology/twitter/9945505/Twitter-in-numbers.html>

⁷¹ Platforms with a similar function and set up as Twitter have been developed in some other countries e.g., Weibo in China.

connected to one another to also exchange information. This exchange may be in the form of text, image or video and can be of use in all stages of crisis management; preparation, response and recovery.

- Twitter enables users to request and offer assistance by using the site as a communication channel.
- Users can be used to relay information via the use of the “retweet” function; “A Retweet is a re-posting of someone else's Tweet. Twitter's Retweet feature helps you and others quickly share that Tweet with all of your followers”.⁷²
- Twitter can also be used for campaigning purposes; stakeholders such as civil society organisations, can use Twitter to help campaign for their organisation (e.g., to raise money for relief efforts following a crisis).
- Twitter can be used for organisation purposes to engage others in discussions and to help promote good practice in response techniques and preparation activities. It can therefore be a useful tool to help stakeholders respond and organise themselves when faced with a crisis.

Twitter can be accessed via SMS, the web and by a number of mobile devices, thereby enabling users to access Twitter whilst on the move.

3.2.2 Facebook

Launched in February 2004, Facebook was originally a restricted social networking site for students attending Harvard University, USA. The site expanded its reach in March 2004 to students at Stanford, Columbia and Yale. As the site grew in popularity, so too did its reach to the education sector. The reach of Facebook was yet again extended on the 26 September 2006, when it was launched as an open platform, enabling anybody to join.⁷³ Facebook aims to “give people the power to share and make the world more open and connected. People use Facebook to stay connected with friends and family, to discover what’s going on in the world, and to share and express what matters to them”.⁷⁴

Growing in popularity, as of the 31 March 2013, the site announced that it had 1.11 billion active monthly users, 751 million of which access the site using a mobile device. Visitors to the site average 655 million daily users, 79% of which reside outside of the USA, making Facebook one of the world’s most popular social networking sites.⁷⁵

As a tool for crisis management, Facebook has a number of unique features including individual profiles, company pages, groups and events that enable several important functions to be performed to help optimise response to a crisis:

- Facebook enables both one-way and two-way communication, enabling those using the site the opportunity to seek and share information in the preparation, response and recovery of a crisis. For instance, following the travel chaos caused by the eruption of Eyjafjallajökull volcano led to some individuals using Facebook to find out alternative transportation options.⁷⁶

⁷² “FAQs About Retweet (RT)”, *Twitter*, 2013. <https://support.twitter.com/articles/77606-what-is-retweet-rt>

⁷³ “Timeline”, *Facebook Newsroom*, 2013. <http://newsroom.fb.com/Timeline>

⁷⁴ “Key Facts”, *Facebook Newsroom*, 2013. <http://newsroom.fb.com/Key-Facts>

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

⁷⁶ Watson, Hayley, and Finn, Rachel L., “Privacy and ethical implications of the use of social media during a volcanic eruption: some initial thoughts” *Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference*, May 2013.

- They can do so by creating a Facebook profile, page or dedicate group, thereby expanding their reach to a wider number of Facebook users as well as non-members depending on the privacy settings.
- Through the use of a private message, the writing on a profile wall or leaving a comment on another person’s post, Facebook users are able to both request and offer assistance to other Facebook users.
- The “share” function on Facebook enables users to share the information (e.g., alert, photo, video etc.) they receive with their wider networks.
- As with Twitter, Facebook users can use the site to promote a campaign such as gathering support of a civil society organisation, or to raise money for relief efforts.
- The interoperability between Facebook and Twitter also enables users to post their Tweets to their Facebook page, thereby synchronising new media applications.
- Facebook users’ profiles, pages, groups and events can all be selected as a means to help and assist co-ordination efforts in responding to a crisis.

As with Twitter, Facebook can be accessed via SMS, the web and via a number of mobile devices, all of which enable users to access Facebook whilst being mobile.

3.2.3 Google+

The Google+ project was launched in June 2011.⁷⁷ Unlike other social network sites, Google+ enables users to filter sharing to different “circles”—network groups that the user specifies according to their preferences. For instance, what a user may want to share with their closest friends may be very different to what they would like to share with their colleagues or parents. Thus Google+ enables selective sharing.⁷⁸

As with Facebook and Twitter, Google+ is able to perform similar functions, including; One-way and two-way communication via its multi-person video calls, sharing of information, initiating conversations and instant messaging. In addition Google+ offers individuals the ability to request and offer assistance, relay information, set up and promote a campaign and to help stakeholders organise themselves to respond to a crisis.

Currently, within crisis response, Google+ does not appear to be as widely used in the response phases of a disaster. Rather, Google+, and particularly its hangout (video conferencing) feature seems to be a useful application for stakeholders to prepare and reflect upon crises. For instance, Google hangout was recently used in June 2013 by the US National Press Foundation to consider the use of (other) Google crisis response tools to help aid journalists in responding to a crisis. The hangout, which was recorded and uploaded to YouTube, remains available for others to view.⁷⁹

Figure 11: Google hangout - National Press Foundation

⁷⁷ “Our History in Depth”, Google, 2013. <http://www.google.com/about/company/history/>

⁷⁸ Gundotra, Vic, “Introducing the Google+ project: Real-life sharing, rethought for the web”, *Google Official Blog*, 28 June 2011. <http://googleblog.blogspot.co.uk/2011/06/introducing-google-project-real-life.html>

⁷⁹ Schneider, Vanessa, “National Press Foundation Hangout: Google Crisis Response and Tools for Media”, 13 June 2013. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6NXbhG6YCMg#at=51>

Furthermore, as with Facebook and Twitter, Google+ is available to users across the globe, both via standard web access and for those on the go via mobile devices.

3.2.4 YouTube

 On the 9 October 2006, Google announced its acquisition of the video playing and sharing social networking website, YouTube. YouTube was originally founded in February 2005 and was, and remains, the world's most popular video sharing site.⁸⁰

YouTube attracts more than 1 billion unique visitors per month, 70% of which comes from users outside of the US, with YouTube having localised sites in 56 counties across 61 languages. YouTube users upload approximately 100 hours of video every minute; and over six billion hours of videos are watched each month. As with other social networking sites, users are able to access YouTube via mobile devices, with 25% of viewing on YouTube occurring via mobile devices (more than one billion views a day).

YouTube provides a unique tool for crisis response in that it enables the sharing of visual images and video content. It is therefore a key tool for one-way and two-way communication, as well as for campaigning purposes. Rather than simply relaying text, those co-ordinating and sharing information, ranging from crisis managers and civil society organisations to members of the public, are able to share information in a much more visually stimulating way and furthermore, those viewing this content can leave comments and participate in a discussion concerning the content, as well as sharing links to videos via other social networking sites (e.g., Google+, Twitter etc.). Furthermore, sharing visual information enhances the (perceived) credibility of the information. Unfortunately, this can be abused for the dissemination of fake images and video, and therefore requires viewers to maintain critical awareness when viewing and further sharing.

YouTube is available to users across the globe, both via standard web access and for those with access to mobile devices.

3.2.5 Reddit

Launched in June 2005, Reddit is an open source, global, online community. Reddit users can create and share content, or create sub-communities where other users can then vote and comment on content, to determine whether the content is important. The content with the most votes rises to the top of the list on the Reddit home page, showing its perceived importance and popularity.⁸¹ As of the 25 July 2013, Reddit had in the previous month received 70,017,371 unique visitors from 183 countries across the globe, viewing a total of 4,567,928,584 pages.⁸²

As a tool for crisis response, Reddit appears to be more readily used by members of the public and emergent online volunteer communities. It has been used by its members to share incident related information, as well as news updates. The number of tools at users' disposal enables Reddit to potentially perform a number of functions including: one-way and two-way communication (in that users can post information as well as participate in the discussion of

⁸⁰ Google, "Google To Acquire YouTube for \$1.65 Billion in Stock", *Google: News from google*, 9 October 2006. http://googlepress.blogspot.co.uk/2006/10/google-to-acquire-youtube-for-165_09.html

⁸¹ "About Reddit", 2013. <http://www.reddit.com/about/>

⁸² Ibid.

information through forums and comments). For example, through the use of the forum feature on Reddit, users can also utilise the site to request and offer assistance in an emergency situation. Furthermore, individuals can relay information they consume on Reddit by sharing it across other social networking platforms. Reddit can also be used for campaign and organising purposes, making it a useful social networking tool in a crisis.

As with other social networking applications, Reddit is available to users across the globe, both via standard web access and for those with access to mobile devices.

3.2.6 Blog

A popular tool for sharing crisis related news and updates is through the use of a blog. A blog is “a personal webpage in a journal format, using software that automatically puts new entries (‘posts’) at the top of the page, and shifts old entries to archives after a specified time, or when the number of posts becomes too large for convenient scrolling”.⁸³

There are a number of freely available blog hosting sites, including (for instance) WordPress and Google’s Blogger. Users can post a range of content to a blog including text, images, links to other sites and video content. Furthermore, many blogs are capable of incorporating social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter, enabling them to bridge the different tools for communicating and opening up dialogue and raising awareness among different audiences.

The use of a blog in responding to a crisis can fulfil a number of functions, including: one-way and two-way communication (via the comment feature), the request and provision of assistance, the sharing of information (by using other social networking tools such as Facebook and Twitter to share information) and campaigning and organising (e.g., a space for publicising information including relief activities and preparation guidance).

In order to write or comment on a blog post, users and viewers can use the web as well as mobile devices.

Social networking applications offer a range of stakeholders a unique combination of additional functions. Crucially, in crisis situations, social networking applications provide stakeholders with a means of communicating and sharing digital content in real-time, across multiple devices. Many of these social networking applications are available to use via the web and mobile applications. A central feature of a social networking application is its ability to connect global networks of existing and emerging social relations, providing extensive opportunities for the more effective and integrative management of crises across different stakeholders groups.

⁸³ Quiggin, J. “Blogs, wikis and creative innovation”. *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, Vol., 9, No. 4, 2006, pp. 481-96. [p. 482]

3.3 WEB TOOLS AND CROWDSOURCING APPLICATIONS

In addition to social networking sites, there are also those applications which are web-based tools. Whilst some of these tools can be accessed using a mobile device, they predominantly require web access (Wi-Fi, 3G or 4G) to be able to use them when responding to, preparing for, or recovering from a crisis.⁸⁴ This sub-section also describes a series of tools that are web-based but focused around “crowdsourcing”.

The term “crowdsourcing” was first employed by Wired magazine writer, Jeff Howe in 2006.⁸⁵ Crowdsourcing refers to “the practice of obtaining needed services, ideas, or content by soliciting contributions from a large group of people and especially from the online community rather than from traditional employees or suppliers”.⁸⁶ Thus in relation to crisis management, crowdsourcing refers to those individuals, often volunteers, who choose to use their skills and knowledge to perform certain tasks that contribute to the response efforts in a crisis.

As argued by OCHA, crowdsourcing can be useful for solving problems as well as to provide information. In relation to humanitarian activities, there are two main forms of crowdsourcing: “one in which information is sought directly from affected communities...and another in which technical or information management tasks, such as mapping or geo-tagging, are outsourced to a “crowd” of volunteers that can live anywhere”.⁸⁷

In order for volunteer groups, such as Crisis Mappers⁸⁸ (a global technology humanitarian network of online volunteers) to effectively respond to a crisis, they must utilise a series of applications to help them complete their tasks. There are currently a range of tools being used by those involved in crowdsourcing activities in crisis management, particularly Google Crisis Response tools and the use of the Ushahidi platform (among others).

Due to the interconnectedness between crowdsourcing and web tools, both of these “primary” forms of applications will be discussed here.

3.3.1 Google crisis response

Google became increasingly involved in crisis response efforts following the devastation caused by Hurricane Katrina in the USA in 2005. By partnering with response organisations, Google have aimed to develop tools for responders to be able to more readily share crisis related information, and to respond to crises in a quick and efficient manner. Google crisis response is a global effort, with many of its tools being developed in multiple languages. A

⁸⁴ Image courtesy of Wayda Dreamscape, Flickr; 26 November 2009.

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/waydadreamscape/4135479176/in/photolist-6m8k9T-6meAoQ-6KAqga-7irpT7-a27prX-anLa5P-aK5M7z-c5v9Q7-7ULbm7/>

⁸⁵ Howe, Jeff, “The rise of crowdsourcing”, *Wired Magazine*, Issue 14.06, June 2006.

<http://www.wired.com/wired/archive/14.06/crowds.html>

⁸⁶ “Crowdsourcing”, *Miriam Webster Online Dictionary*, 2013. <http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/crowdsourcing>

⁸⁷ *Humanitarianism in the Network Age: Including World Humanitarian Data and Trends 2012*, Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), 2013.

<https://ochanet.unocha.org/p/Documents/WEB%20Humanitarianism%20in%20the%20Network%20Age%20vF%20single.pdf>

⁸⁸ Crisis Mappers.net, 2013. <http://crisismappers.net/>

dedicated project by Google, Google Crisis Response consists of a team of staff including engineers, project managers and partnership professionals dedicated to crisis response.⁸⁹

Google Crisis Response includes seven web based tools, some of which are also available as mobile applications. All of Google’s crisis response tools have been used following a number of crises, including; the September 2010 earthquake in New Zealand and the earthquake and tsunami in Japan in 2011.⁹⁰ The tools include:

Google Public Alerts functions as a form of one-way communication by enabling responders to share relevant emergency alerts to users. Google public alerts are combined with Google Maps to make it easy for users to understand precisely where, geographically, the alert applies and to enable them to organise themselves accordingly to respond to the threat.⁹¹

Figure 12: Google Public Alerts - 31 July 2013

Google person finder is also a crowdsourcing tool. It is a collaborative platform that functions as a form of one-way communication, enabling stakeholders to assist each other in the event of people being separated by a crisis. This platform can be used by responders and individuals to assist in organising and planning to identify and locate missing persons. Google person finder can be accessed using the web as well as through any mobile device that enables users to access the web.⁹²

Figure 13: Google Person Finder - Test - Japan

Figure 14: Custom Google Maps

Custom Google maps is also a crowdsourcing tool, enabling users to collaborate to provide rich and valuable information in a crisis situation (e.g., using geo-tagging to map events or resources that might be required). Google maps are fully customizable, enabling users to use the tool to perform a series of functions within crisis management. As a tool, it enables one-way communication when used with another service (e.g., Google Alerts). It enables individuals to request and offer assistance, and it assists a range of stakeholders including response organisations, individuals and

⁸⁹ “Google Crisis Response: FAQ”, Google.org, no date. <http://www.google.org/crisisresponse/faq.html>

⁹⁰ “Google Crisis Response: For responders”, Google.org, no date. <http://www.google.org/crisisresponse/resources.html> [Further information and case studies of the use of these tools can be found on the Google Crisis Response website].

⁹¹ Google Public Alerts, Google.org, 31 July 2013. <http://google.org/publicalerts>

⁹² Google Person Finder, Google.org, 2013. <http://www.google.org/personfinder/global/home.html>

authorities to organise themselves before, during and after a crisis (e.g., by finding route directions). Google maps can be accessed using both the web and via mobile devices.⁹³

Google earth is a customisable tool for those responding to a crisis as it allows them greater geographical data regarding the location of a crisis, and is therefore a useful tool for organisation purposes. As with other Google response tools, Google earth can be accessed using both web and mobile devices.⁹⁴

Google fusion tables is an experimental data visualisation application that enables users to gather, visualise and share large data tables.⁹⁵ Stakeholders can use Google fusion tables to assist them in their organisation efforts in responding to and understanding a crisis. For example, following the 2011 London riots, the tool was used to identify data patterns by embedding the data into a map to show indices of deprivation in relation to where the riots were taking place.⁹⁶ As with other tools, Google fusion tables can be accessed via the web or by a mobile device.

Figure 15: Google fusion table of 2011

Google docs and spreadsheets allows stakeholders to “create, collaborate and continually update critical information online from any computer at any point in time” thereby assisting them to organise prepare for, respond to and recover from a crisis.⁹⁷ By accessing Google docs and spreadsheets via the web and associated mobile applications, users can remain up-to-date and collaborate with other responders without the need to e-mail documents back and forth.

Google sites allow stakeholders to build and easily maintain a website, allowing them to participate in one-way communication (e.g., status updates regarding a crisis) and to provide information (e.g., a map of the location of the crisis, images etc.) to others to help them to organise themselves to more effectively respond to an on-going crisis.⁹⁸

3.3.2 Airbnb

AirBnB was founded in 2008. It is a virtual marketplace for individuals to “list, discover, and book unique accommodations around the world — online or from a mobile phone”.⁹⁹ The application has been used in 33,000 cities in 192 countries.

Following the success of Airbnb in everyday situations, the devastation caused by Hurricane Sandy in October 2012 in the USA presented the application with an opportunity to assist those in need of shelter. The Airbnb organisation and hosts offered its service for free to help those affected by the storm and to help house and connect those that had been displaced by the crisis. In this manner, Airbnb functions as a platform that those both directly and indirectly affected by a crisis can call upon to request and offer assistance in the form of

⁹³ Custom Google Maps, *Google.org*, 2013.

<https://support.google.com/maps/topic/1687289?hl=en&parent=1687360>

⁹⁴ Google Earth, *Google.org*, 2013. http://www.google.co.uk/intl/en_uk/earth/index.html

⁹⁵ “Google Crisis Response: For responders”, no date.

⁹⁶ Stiles, Matt, *No name*, no date. <http://mattstiles.es/viz/london.html>

⁹⁷ “Google Crisis Response: For responders”, no date.

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹⁹ “About Airbnb”, *Airbnb*, 2013. <https://www.airbnb.co.uk/about>

shelter, and to help others by empowering them to organise themselves in responding to a crisis.¹⁰⁰

Figure 16: Airbnb Disaster Response

3.3.3 AMBER alert Europe

AMBER alert is based on the crowdsourcing-initiative; the Dutch AMBER alert system¹⁰¹. AMBER alert Europe enables European countries without a similar system to create a Child Rescue alert system for cross-border alerting purposes. The service has 2 million registered members in the EU and aims to “save lives when a child goes missing, is abducted or is a victim of trafficking anywhere in Europe”.¹⁰²

The web based tool functions as a form of one-way communication, alerting its members to missing children by also showing the last known location of the missing person on a Google customised map. Members of the site can receive alerts via a range of means including SMS and e-mail. The site also functions as a communication medium for requesting help and encourages users to provide assistance by getting in touch if they have any relevant information of a missing child’s status. Visitors to the site are also able to share news of a missing child via their social networking profiles (e.g., Facebook and Twitter).

3.3.4 European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre

Among other monitoring and research activities, the European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre (EMSC) hosts a web-based tool that functions as a notification system. EMSC collects real time seismological data from over 65 seismological networking in the Euro-Med region. If a potentially destructive earthquake occurs, EMSC initiates a notification alert in which an e-mail, SMS or fax message can be sent to registered end-users within 20-30 minutes of the earthquake occurring. This alert would contain location based information of the earthquake, thereby providing a unique source of information to European and International organisations. In this manner, the service functions as a form of one-way communication.¹⁰³

¹⁰⁰ “Airbnb Disaster Response”, *Airbnb*, 2013. <https://www.airbnb.co.uk/disaster-response>

¹⁰¹ *AMBER Alert Netherlands*, 2013. <http://www.amberalertnederland.nl/Default.aspx?lang=en>

¹⁰² “About Us”, *AMBER alert Europe*, 2013. <http://www.amberalert.eu/AboutUs.aspx>

¹⁰³ “Real Time Information and Earthquake Notification services”, *European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre*, 2010. http://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/seismicity/real_time.php

Figure 17: EMSC - Real Time Seismicity

3.3.5 Natuurbrandgevaar

Figure 18: Natuurbrandgevaar website

Natuurbrandgevaar is a website in the Netherlands that operates, in real-time, as a form of one-way communication, enabling visitors to understand the potential risks they may face of wildfires in different regions of the country. In this manner, the site potentially assists stakeholders to respond and organise themselves to emerging threats. Users can access the site via the web or via mobile devices.¹⁰⁴

3.3.6 Ushahidi

Ushahidi is a Swahili word that means “testimony”. Ushahidi are a non-profit technology company that specialise in free and open sourced software development in the form of information collection, visualisation and interactive mapping.

The Ushahidi website was initially set up in the mist of the 2008 Kenya post-election fallout, where President Mwai Kibaki’s victory appeared to be rified, resulting in vicious riots and looting across the country. During the fallout, Okolloh, a native of Kenya with a law degree from Harvard, kept a blog about politics in Kenya. As part of her blogging efforts, she received many updates from political parties, journalist and other sources in Parliament. Inundated with information, Okolloh put a call out to computer scientists to help with a mash-up that would allow violence and destruction to be mapped onto Google Earth, resulting in the birth of the Ushahidi platform. Ushahidi consisted of a website that collected eyewitness reports and mapped them online.¹⁰⁵

Since 2008, Ushahidi have developed crowd mapping platforms, in multiple languages including the Ushahidi platform and Crowd Map. Both of these platforms are accessible via the web, mobile devices and via SMS.¹⁰⁶ By using either of these platforms stakeholders can perform several functions including; one-way communication via the sharing of information,

¹⁰⁴ *Natuurbrandgevaar*, 2 August 2013, <http://www.natuurbrandgevaar.nl/>

¹⁰⁵ Bahree, Megha, “Citizen Voices”, *Forbes*, November 29, 2008. <http://www.forbes.com/global/2008/1208/114.html>.

¹⁰⁶ “About us”, *Ushahidi*, 2013. <http://www.ushahidi.com/about-us>

request and provide assistance and organise response efforts by mapping relevant information in real-time.

3.3.7 Ubalert

Ubalert is a disaster alert network. It consists of a social network of individuals, working together via crowdsourcing activities to share knowledge of the world's crises that could affect the security of citizens. In addition to their web presence, Ubalert have also developed a global emergency platform (mobile app) that “validates the reliability of the reported content and then immediately alerts those who may be impacted, depending on the severity and location”.¹⁰⁷

Figure 19: Ubalert – Website

Ubalert has several functions that can contribute to the management of crises, including; 1) providing disaster related alert information, making it a suitable application for one-way communication; 2) through its comment feature which enables two-way communication, individuals can converse about disaster specific event; 3) via its share feature, individuals can share information to their other social networks; 4) by being able to receive and find out disaster specific information stakeholders can begin to organise themselves to respond to an approaching crisis.

Figure 20: Ubalert mobile app

Ubalert can be accessed via a range of applications including the web and via mobile applications.

Distinctive from social network applications, the web tools and crowdsourcing applications discussed in this sub-section include specific tools and platforms that stakeholders can use for different purposes in responding to and managing crisis. In this way, when compared to social networking applications they are less focused around communication and social networks and more focused on providing a service (e.g., mapping a crisis). It is important to note that the applications that are based around crowdsourcing activities rely on individuals forming like-minded networks for the applications to be of use to respond and manage a crisis.

3.4 MOBILE TOOLS

The use of new media tools to aid crisis management also includes mobile tools that users can access via devices such as smart phones and tablet devices.¹⁰⁸ Such devices enable individuals to access new media applications whilst on the move, and reduced the limitations placed on them for accessing and sharing information. Users are also able to

¹⁰⁷ “About us”, *Ubalert*, 2013. http://www.ubalert.com/about_us

¹⁰⁸ Image courtesy of Jeremy Keith on Flickr, 16 September 2011. <http://goo.gl/rZIJON>

benefit from other functions that mobile applications offer. It is important to note that some of the other applications already discussed in this chapter, including the majority of social networking sites and other web tools (e.g., Ushahidi and Google Maps) can be accessed via mobile devices, although they were originally designed for use by desktop devices. Accordingly, the tools discussed in this section are primarily accessed by mobile devices.

3.4.1 American Red Cross Apps

The American Red Cross (ARC) have spent a significant amount of time and effort in developing its own range of mobile applications to help individuals organise themselves to prepare and respond to different types of crisis situations. They have developed six applications: Hurricane App, Tornado App, Wildfire App, Earthquake App, First Aid App and the Shelter Finder App.¹⁰⁹

The applications are predominantly useful as a one-way communication device, informing individuals of forthcoming crises thereby helping them to organise themselves to adequately respond to potential threats. The crisis specific applications assist users’ organisation skills by incorporating a learning module into the app. The learning module provides users with preparatory information relating to specific crises. For instance, the Hurricane app, provides users with information about how to prepare for a hurricane including crisis specific information such as a plan of action and knowing the difference between a hurricane watch and a hurricane warning.

Figure 21: American Red Cross - Hurricane App

There is also a function in the crisis specific applications that enable users to declare the status of their personal situation as to whether they are safe or not. In addition, the application has a sharing function enabling it to work in tandem with other applications including social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter. Finally, the applications enable users to donate financial aid to on-going crises, thereby serving a campaign function.

The following table summarises the functionality of each application:

Table 3: American Red Cross Mobile Apps

Application	Function(s)
Hurricane app	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Organise/Campaign
Tornado app	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Organise/Campaign
Wildfire app	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Organise/Campaign
Earthquake app	One-way communication/Request and offer assistance/Organise/Campaign
Shelter view	One-way communication/Organise
First aid app	One-way communication/Organise

¹⁰⁹ On the 18 July 2013, the American Red Cross announced the launch of its latest app; Team Red Cross, which aims to recruit volunteers to respond to emerging crises to assist their community. <http://www.redcross.org/news/press-release/American-Red-Cross-Launches-New-App-to-Recruit-Volunteers>

3.4.2 Disaster alert

Disaster alert is an application by the Pacific Disaster Center and was first launched in July 2010. The application provides users with a list and map of active hazards (those that are current and occurring in real-time) around the world. As well as being a form of one-way communication (by providing information), the app also enables users to relay information by sharing it via their other applications (e.g., e-mail, social networks etc.). The app is available to users with access to adequate mobile devices.¹¹⁰

Figure 22: Disaster alert app

3.4.3 Earthquake

Figure 23:
Earthquake app

Earthquake is a comprehensive crowdsourcing application that allows reporting agencies to share earthquake and tsunami alerts with users in real-time. As with the disaster alert application, Earthquake enables information to be posted and viewed on a live map. As an application for one-way communication, users are able to contribute and report their own information based on an experience they may have with an earthquake. The application also enables users to share information with others based on its integration of Facebook and Twitter search functions. Combined, these features enable individuals to organise themselves to respond to imminent earthquakes and tsunamis.¹¹¹

3.4.4 NL-Alert

NL-Alert is an initiative by the Dutch government that functions as a form of one-way communication in the form of a cell broadcast sent directly to individuals that might be in the vicinity of an emergency situation. The message informs individuals of the current situation and what they can do to respond, thereby assisting individuals to organise themselves and respond to a potential crisis. In order to make use of the alert system, individuals are required to activate the cell broadcast service on their mobile device. NL-Alert is compatible with Commercial Mobile Alert Systems (CMAS) and EU-Alert.¹¹²

3.4.5 Red panic button

The red panic button application was launched in March 2011 and enables users to sign up to the application -and register their emergency contact details. In this way, the application acts as a form of one-way communication and enables users to request help should they then need it. Should users require assistance, the application allows them to “push the red button” and then it will automatically send an SMS, e-mail and potentially a social networking alert (depending on their accounts) with a link via Google maps with their GPS coordinates to the contacts in their dedicated contact list.¹¹³

Figure 24: The
Red panic button
app

¹¹⁰ “Disaster alert app”, *Pacific Disaster Center*, 19 November 2012.

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=disasterAlert.PDC&hl=en>

¹¹¹ “Earthquake”, *Mobeetio Inc*, 26 June 2012. <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/earthquake/id304483984?mt=8>

¹¹² *NL-Alert*, 2013. <http://www.nederlandveilig.nl/nl-alert/>

¹¹³ “Features”, *Red Panic Button*, 2012. <http://www.redpanicbutton.com/features.html>

3.4.6 Tsunami early warning

Figure 25: Tsunami early warning app

The Tsunami early warning application was launched in December 2011. The application functions as a form of one-way communication, enabling users to receive early warning notifications of any potential tsunami waves that may cross their path (based on their location). The application calculates “tsunami wave propagation” and sends an SMS message to users if they are in any danger, thereby helping them to organise themselves to prepare for and respond to any potential threats.¹¹⁴

3.4.7 Waze

Figure 26: Use of Waze following Oklahoma tornado (2013)

Founded in 2008, Waze is a community-based traffic and navigation application. By installing the Waze application on your mobile device, individuals can understand and share real-time traffic and road information, supporting others who may be affected by traffic conditions, potentially saving others money and time. In this manner, Waze relies on crowdsourcing to help keep information up-to-date.

Waze therefore functions as a form of one-way communication, and as an application that helps individuals to organise themselves when faced with a crisis.¹¹⁵ For instance, following the tornadoes in Oklahoma in June 2013, individuals were able to use Waze to avoid a collapsed bridge and other areas affected by the tornadoes.¹¹⁶

Distinctive from social network applications (for which app installation is typically optional) and web-based tools, mobile tools require that users download and install applications on their mobile devices for later use. Many of the applications discussed in this sub-section are designed in such a way so as to be used by individuals whilst they are mobile, thereby ensuring, in the first instance, that their functions (e.g. alert mechanism) contribute to securing citizens safety in the event of a crisis.

¹¹⁴ Alibek, J. “Tsunami early warning”, *ISM*, 5 September 2012. <https://itunes.apple.com/ca/app/tsunami-early-warning/id461309574?mt=8>

¹¹⁵ “FAQ”, *Waze*, 2012. <http://www.waze.com/faq/>

¹¹⁶ Daniel, “Waze Map Editors Help Drivers Get Around Collapsed Bridge and Damage from Oklahoma Tornadoes”, *Waze: Blog*, 7 June 2013. <http://www.waze.com/blog/waze-map-editors-help-drivers-get-around-collapsed-bridge-and-damage-from-oklahoma-tornadoes/>

3.5 CONCLUSION

The aim of this chapter has been to provide the COSMIC project and its stakeholders with a baseline analysis of new media applications that are currently used within the management and response to crises.

In total 31 applications have been identified; six of which were primarily social networking websites, a further nine were classified as web tools, four were identified as being primarily crowdsourcing applications and 12 as mobile tools.

When breaking this classification down according to how individuals can access them (some applications could be accessed by multiple means), the most popular form was the mobile applications category (30 mobile applications), and the least popular was the SMS utility of applications (5 applications).

Crucially, this chapter has also been able to identify the functionality behind the different applications, enabling stakeholders to understand the pros and cons of using different applications for different purposes.

- The majority of applications, 30 out of 31, were capable of performing one-way communication.
- The majority of applications, 28 out of 31, were capable of assisting stakeholders with organisation efforts in a crisis.

- Some applications, 13 out of 31, were able to allow users to request and offer assistance. One application was only able to offer users the ability to seek assistance.
- Ten applications enable individuals to relay (share) information.
- Seven applications allowed for two-way communication; thereby expanding the abilities of different stakeholders to communicate in a crisis.

Thus it is evident that applications provide different functionality that may or may not be suitable for responding to a crisis. It is important to note that the findings of this chapter suggest that a “one size fits all” approach does not apply to the use of new media applications in crisis situations. Rather, stakeholders should consider their individual needs in crises and utilise the appropriate applications to meet those needs.

For instance in preparing for and responding to a flood, it is not enough for crisis managers to use a social networking site such as Twitter to share information up-dates and respond to some individuals enquiries. Rather, they should also utilise other tools including those offered by Google Crisis Response, such as Google Maps, Google Public Alerts, as well as those tools that enable users to contribute to mapping a crisis, such as Ushahidi. In the event of the vast flooding of homes, applications such as Airbnb offer individuals a useful way of finding temporary accommodation.

Figure 27: New media applications - flood scenario

Crucially, the availability of various applications is not enough to aid crisis response, what is necessary, is for applications to be utilised by stakeholders. Accordingly, the following chapter, Chapter 4, will assess stakeholder use of different ICT tools and new media applications to understand which applications may be better suited to reach a wider audience, thereby being of greater use for a wide range of stakeholders to use in a crisis.

4 KEY STAKEHOLDERS & USAGE TRENDS

It is evident that there are a range of information communication technologies and new media applications that are currently available to stakeholders to use in the management of crises. Chapters 2 and 3 of this report have provided a baseline analysis of the various communication technologies that are available to stakeholders, building on these findings, the present chapter will seek to highlight which stakeholders are using new media applications. In addition, partners will highlight any noticeable trends in usage and adoption as well as commenting on the intended use (that is what the system was originally designed to do), as opposed to the actual use of new media applications.

4.1 STAKEHOLDER USE OF NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS

As highlighted in Chapter 3, there are a range of existing new media applications available to stakeholders to use in crisis situations, yet, it is not yet clear “who” is using different types of applications. Drawing on the findings of COSMIC’s D5.1, “Stakeholder engagement strategy”, particularly the “broad” categories of stakeholders, this chapter seeks to understand which of the stakeholders identified in D5.1 are using new media applications.¹¹⁷ This identification involved partners examining a series of incident related journal articles, news articles and trade magazines.

As identified in D5.1, broad stakeholder categories involved in the management of crises include:¹¹⁸

- **Government:** This includes representatives from different levels of governmental organisations such as the European Commission, inter-governmental organisations, such as UN and NATO, Member State governments or local governments and their associated decision-makers. This category includes policy-makers, regulatory, legislative, administrative or public authorities. It also includes EU, national and local institutions and agencies, for example transport, communications, utilities, etc. A key subset of this category is crisis management agencies and personnel within national and local governments, including crisis managers and first responders.
- **The media:** This category includes all kinds of communications platforms such as television, radio, newspapers, magazines, journals, blogs, and websites. This would also include journalists’ organisations such as national unions as well as citizen journalism organisations (e.g., All Voices, Global Voices Online, etc.).
- **Civil society organisations (CSOs):** This includes independent, non-governmental organisations bringing people together with a common cause, such as umbrella organisations of first responders and crisis managers (e.g., national fire fighters’ associations) as well as charities, political advocacy organisations, humanitarian organisations (e.g., The Red Cross), etc. It also includes non-profit organisations (or the non-profit arms of commercial organisations) that are active in crisis communication (e.g., Twitcident, Google Crisis Response, etc.)
- **Industry:** This includes companies providing crisis management, communication and social media solutions through research and development as well as critical infrastructure providers,

¹¹⁷ Finn, Rachel, Watson, Hayley, Wadhwa, Kush, Lianos, Alex, Papadimitriou, Alex, Spyroglou Odysseas, Miskuf Robert and Bonnamour, Marie-Christine, “Stakeholder engagement strategy”, *D5.1 of the COSMIC project*, 30 July 2013. [pp. 8-9]

¹¹⁸ Partners have chosen not included two categories: project partners and academics, as this does not necessarily include those that are directly involved with crisis response activities.

manufacturers, suppliers, distributors and retailers of key goods, service providers and industry associations.

- **The public:** This refers to the ordinary people in society.

Accordingly, as far as possible, the following table illustrates which “known” stakeholders are using new media applications. Partners identified “known” use of applications by assessing news items, incident reports, and journal articles and by examining, where possible, the applications explanatory, accompanying documentation.

Table 4: Stakeholder use of new media applications

Name	Primary application	Key dates	Stakeholders using application(s)	Example
Twitter	Social networking	Launched globally - March 2007	Government/Media/CSO's/Industry/Public	Hurricane sandy (October 2012)
Facebook	Social networking	Launched globally - September 2006	Government/Media/CSO's/Industry/Public	Hurricane sandy (October 2012)
Google public alerts	Web tool	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	Government/CSO's/Industry	Severe thunderstorm warning (Missouri, August 2013)
Google person finder	Crowdsourcing	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	Government/Media/CSO's/Industry/Public	Japan earthquake & Tsunami (March 2011)
Custom Google maps	Crowdsourcing	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	Government/Media/CSO's/Industry/Public	New Zealand earthquake (September 2010)
Google earth	Web tool	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	CSO's	International medical corps - Haiti earthquake (2010)
Google fusion tables	Web tool	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	Media/Industry	The Guardian - London Riots (August 2011)
Google docs and spreadsheets	Web tool	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	Government/CSO's	Americorps - Joplin tornado (May 2011)
Google sites	Web tool	Post - August 2005 (Hurricane Katrina)	CSO's	Save the Children (on-going)
Airbnb	Web tool	October 2012 (Hurricane Sandy)	Public	Hurricane sandy (October 2012)
Waze	Mobile tool	2008	Public	Oklahoma tornado (2013)
Hurricane by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	July 2012	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
Tornado by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	February 2013	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
Wildfire by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	January 2013	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
Earthquake by American Red	Mobile tool	September 2012	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>

Cross				
American Red Cross: Shelter View	Mobile tool	February 2011	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
First Aid App by American Red Cross	Mobile tool	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
YouTube	Social networking	February 2005	Government/Media/CSO's/Industry/Public	Eyjafjallajökull volcanic eruption (March-April 2010)
Reddit	Social networking	June 2005	Public	Boston marathon attacks (April 2013)
Ushahidi	Crowdsourcing	2008	Media/CSO's/Public	Crisis mappers UK - London 2012 Olympics
Google+	Social networking	June 2011	CSO's	British Red Cross - On-going
Blogs	Social networking	1999+	CSO's/Public	American Red Cross - On-going
Ubalert	Web tool	August 2011	Government/Media/CSO's/Industry/Public	Earthquake New Zealand (August 2013)
Tsunami early warning	Mobile tool	December 2011	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
Red panic button	Mobile tool	March 2011	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
Earthquake	Mobile tool	June 2010	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
Disaster Alert	Mobile tool	July 2010	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
NL-alert	Mobile tool	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	Netherlands (On-going)
AMBER alert Europe	Crowdsourcing	March 2013	Government/CSO's	On-going
Natuurbrandgevaar	Web tool	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>
European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	Web tool	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>

Further in-depth information relating to stakeholder use of new media applications will be supplied in D2.2 “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”.

4.1.1 Social networking applications

Social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter were not originally tools that were designed for crisis management activities. Rather, as outlined in Chapter 3, they were designed to open up communication and sharing online and to connect people across the globe through existing and new social networks. It is such features (e.g., instant communication, photo and video sharing etc.) along with the increase in the popularity of these new social networks that has contributed to their adoption in crisis management.

In Europe for instance, as revealed by the 2012 “Special Eurobarometer: Cyber security”, Internet use by Europeans is widespread and frequent. A minority of citizens do not use the Internet (29%), the majority use the Internet at least once a week: once a week (3%), several

times a week (10%), once a day (14%) and several times a day (39%).¹¹⁹ When online, 52% of Europeans were found to access and use social networking sites. Use of social networking sites was found to be highest in Latvia (69%), Malta (68%) and Greece (68%) as well as in Slovakia (66%).¹²⁰ Thus, in terms of stakeholder use of social networking sites, on a regular basis there is evidence to suggest that the public are indeed active users of social networking applications.

In relation to the use of social networking sites in a crisis situation, the amount of evidence available based on Europeans usage is somewhat limited. There are some studies that have shown that Europeans are using social networking sites in a crisis, this was seen for instance following the Eyjafjallajokull volcano in 2010. Social networking sites such as Twitter were used by those members of the public affected by the travel chaos, as well as those responding to the chaos, including airlines and the European Organisation for the Safety of Air Navigation (EUROCONTROL).¹²¹

In the UK, during the summer of 2013, when confronted with extreme temperatures government departments, authorities, industry (e.g., water providers) and the media utilised social networking sites to provide information to citizens (e.g., how to keep cool as well as advisory information such as drinking lots of fluids) as well as participating in other activities including alerts (e.g., where free water could be accessed and expected temperatures as well as rainfall and storm alerts).

British Red Cross (19 July 2013) – Drinking fluids, wearing light coloured clothes & keeping out of the sun are the best ways to keep cool #FridayFirstAid #heatwave

London Prepared (22 July 2013) - Free water bottles at Waterloo Station - #BeatTheHeat

In the US, an infographic by the University of San Francisco demonstrates the increasing popularity of social networking sites for responding to crisis, providing evidence of the use of social networking sites by: the public and those involved in emergency response including the government (authorities) and civil society organisations.¹²²

Figure 28: Infographic by the University of San Francisco

¹¹⁹ TNS Opinion & Social, “Special Eurobarometer: Cyber security”, *European Commission*, July 2012. http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/archives/ebs/ebs_390_en.pdf

¹²⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 18.

¹²¹ Watson, H., and Finn, R, “Privacy and ethical implications of the use of social media during a volcanic eruption: some initial thoughts.” *Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference*, May 2013, Baden-Baden, Germany.

¹²² “Social media: the new face of disaster response”, *University of San Francisco: Online master of public administration*, no date. <http://onlinempa.usfca.edu/social-media/> [Please see the appendix for the full version of the infographic].

This is further exemplified by the use of social networking sites following the Japanese earthquake and tsunami in 2011:

Figure 29: Infographic by the University of San Francisco

There are also those civil society organisations who are using social networking sites as part of their on-going engagement with different stakeholders to promote their activities, campaigns and other health and safety related information. For instance, in the UK, the British Red Cross use a range of social networking sites including Facebook, Twitter and Google+ to share information relating to preparedness and response. Their Google+ account currently includes updates about their activities, as well as information relating to how people can prepare for on-going emergencies (e.g., the 2013 summer heat wave in the UK).

Figure 30: British Red Cross on Google+

Elsewhere, members of the public have turned to the social networking site, Reddit to share information about the devastating train crash in Spain in July 2013. For instance, one Reddit user posted an image, which showed people lining up to donate blood to those needed. As of the 25 July 2013, the post had received 3,235 votes making it the second most popular piece of content on the website.¹²³

¹²³ Reddit, 25 July 2013. <http://i.imgur.com/PGRBfwt.jpg>

Figure 31: Reddit - 25 July 2013

Elsewhere, in the aftermath of the earthquake in Van (Turkey) social media provided ample opportunity for citizen involvement in search and rescue and aid provision in the aftermath of the Van Earthquake. For example, the aid movement #EvimEvinDirVan (#myhomeisyourhomeVan) initiated through Twitter was reported to have drawn around 17,000 volunteers who wanted to provide temporary housing (at their own houses) to victims of the Earthquake.¹²⁴

Thus it is evident from the examples cited here (and many more, as will be identified in D2.2) that different types of stakeholders are actively using social networking sites as a communication and dissemination channel in a crisis situation.

4.1.2 Web tools and crowdsourcing applications

Web tools identified in Chapter 3 such as, Google Maps, Google Earth and Airbnb were not developed as tools to be used for crisis management. Rather, they were developed and designed for public every-day use (as seen with regard to social networking applications). However, there are some web tools discussed in chapter three, including the Ushahidi platform and AMBER alert system that have been purposefully designed to contribute to assisting crisis management activities.

A review of documents suggest that currently web tools are predominantly used by civil society organisations, this was particularly evident of Google's series of crisis response tools. For instance, following the earthquake and Tsunami in Japan in 2011 members of the public used Google's Person Finder to locate members of their family.¹²⁵ Elsewhere the CSO, Doctors Without Borders used Google Earth to help them visualise the origins of the cholera outbreak following the earthquake in Haiti in 2010.¹²⁶ Elsewhere, following the Joplin tornado in the US in 2011, the US government organisation, Americorps used Google spreadsheets for administrative purposes to track volunteers, saving them valuable time and resources.¹²⁷

¹²⁴ Ergurel, Deniz, "Teknoloji hayata baglar (technology connects to life)", *Samanyolu Haber*, 29 October 2011. <http://teknoloji.samanyoluhaber.com/haberler/712141/Teknoloji-hayata-baglar/>

¹²⁵ "Toshiko in the Japan Earthquake: Google Person Finder", *Google Crisis Response*, 2011. http://www.google.org/crisisresponse/pdfs/toshiko_japan_case_study.pdf

¹²⁶ "Doctors Without Borders in the Haiti Earthquake: Google Earth", *Google Crisis Response*, 2011. http://www.google.org/crisisresponse/pdfs/doctorswithoutborders_haiti_case_study.pdf

¹²⁷ "Americorps, Joplin, US Tornado", *Google.org*, 30 August 2011. <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qeu5aNFWTls&feature=relmfu>

Web tools including Ushahidi and Airbnb are also being used by members of the public and news organisations in disaster response. For instance, following Hurricane Sandy in 2012, the Ushahidi crowd map platform was used by the news group, Huffington Post to provide information about relevant evacuations, supplies etc. to its readers.¹²⁸ In addition, as identified in Chapter 3, Hurricane Sandy sparked the use of Airbnb by members of the public to offer temporary shelter to those in need.¹²⁹

Thus it is evident that within crisis response web-based tools are being used by different stakeholders to meet their requirements. Further information relating to the use of these web-based tools will be examined in D2.2 of the COSMIC project.

4.1.3 Mobile tools

The mobile tools assessed in Chapter 3 are specifically designed, tested and developed so as to continue to contribute to crisis management activities. As discussed in Chapter 3, with some applications (e.g., Waze), it is possible to know that some members of the public used the application to help them navigate around the destruction caused by the tornadoes in Oklahoma in June 2013.¹³⁰ It was also possible for partners to identify who were using the AMBER alert application; namely government authorities and civil society organisations were using the application to launch and monitor alerts relating to missing children within Europe.

Unlike the other forms of “primary application” assessed in this chapter, it has not been possible to identify, for many of the mobile applications, which stakeholders are using them. This is largely a result of the lack of available information. For now, we know that these applications exist, however, there is a need for greater transparency to determine the usage and usefulness of these applications.

4.2 CONCLUSION

In order to contribute to COSMIC’s wider understanding of the availability and use of new media applications in crisis management, this chapter has sought to identify which stakeholders are using new media applications. Findings from this chapter have shown that based on the information available, stakeholders using social media fall into five categories: Government, the media, civil society organisations, industry and the public. It is evident that some web based applications and social networking applications were not originally developed to aid crisis response, yet their features are becoming popular tools for crisis management activities.

The following table illustrates the current “known” stakeholder user of different types of new media applications, based on the categorisation of “primary application”.

¹²⁸ “Huffington Post Sandy Stormwatch”, *Crowdmap*, no date. <https://hpsandy.crowdmap.com/>

¹²⁹ “Airbnb Disaster Response”, 2013

¹³⁰ Daniel, 7 June 2013.

Table 5: Stakeholder use of new media applications

	Social networking	Web tools	Crowdsourcing	Mobile tools	Total
Government	3	3	3	0	9
Media	3	2	3	0	8
CSO's	5	5	4	0	14
Industry	3	3	2	0	8
Public	5	2	3	1	11
Unknown	0	2	0	11	13

As can be seen in the table, of the “known” usage, civil society organisations seem to be more likely to engage with the various types of new media applications available than other stakeholders, particularly those in industry and the media.

A crucial finding of this chapter regards the (current) lack of primary data freely available to determine how some new media applications, particularly mobile applications, for crisis management are being used. This grey area of information consequently impairs our understanding of stakeholders’ engagement with new media applications. Accordingly, future research ought to more specifically assess who is using different new media applications in their crisis management activities, and how they are being used. Such knowledge will serve to further complement the incorporation of new media in crisis management activities.

5 CONCLUSION

The ability to communicate and share information prior to, during and following a crisis has dramatically changed over the last decade. No longer limited to information communication technologies including the telephone, radio and television, the development of the Internet and other technologies have led to a surge of new media applications. The purpose of this report has been to provide a baseline analysis of communication technologies and applications that are currently available and in use in crisis situations.

This report involved two research activities that were presented in Chapters 2 and 3: 1) an exploration of the state of the art of communication technologies, and 2) an exploration of the state of the art in new media applications. The findings of which are briefly summarised here.

State of the art of communication technologies

- The convergence of information and communication technologies means that modern communications are not only revolutionising crisis management, but the nature of the role of communication technology within crisis management is also evolving, from ad-hoc focused services, to rich integrated services.
- Functional requirements for communication technologies include; critical components (e.g., voice and text message), basic and important functions (e.g., group voice communication, the transmission of video and images, and the ability to leave a voice message), and those functions that are more specialised and may have a high impact on the services and applications they offer (e.g., the verification of biometric data and Wireless video surveillance and remote monitoring).
- There are also non-functional requirement that address both the active use of the technologies during a crisis, the permanent activities of preparing, training and equipping Government and NGO organisations, as well as individual citizens, to deal with crises if they should occur. Examples include; reliability, resilience, interoperability and standards compliance.
- Authors identified communication technologies as products, defining their functionality and the benefits and barriers of different technologies. Examples of communication technologies included for instance; two-way radio, satellite phone (analogue and digital), amateur radio, commercial broadcasting and the web.
- Authors also discussed the use of sensors with different products to enable greater functionality to communication devices, enabling the collection and communication of rich information that can support emergency operations.
- In support of chapter three, authors also discussed the transformation of viewing communication technologies, not just as products, but as understanding them in terms of their capabilities.
- Authors discussed the need for collaboration and interoperability of communications in a crisis.

- Authors also discussed trends and statistics in the transformation in communication technologies based on their capabilities, which lends itself to the further discussion of new media applications in chapter 3.

State of the art in new media applications

- There are various types of new media applications that can be used in crisis management activities. Partners have identified applications according to their “primary application”, that is what they were originally designed for prior to the vast expansion of mobile applications across devices; social networking applications, web applications and crowdsourcing applications and mobile applications.
- Applications can be accessed via a combination of means, including: SMS, mobile devices and via the Internet (web). The most common form of accessibility included mobile and web applications.
- New media applications have different functions, of which should be respected when stakeholders try to determine what application to use for different purposes:
 - The majority of applications, 30 out of 31, were capable of performing one-way communication.
 - The majority of applications, 28 out of 31, were capable of assisting stakeholders with organisation efforts in a crisis.
 - Some applications, 13 out of 31, were able to allow users to request and offer assistance. One application was only able to offer users the ability to seek assistance.
 - Ten applications enable individuals to relay (share) information.
 - Seven applications allowed for two-way communication; thereby expanding the abilities of different stakeholders to communicate in a crisis.

Chapters 2 and 3 are useful for providing stakeholders with further information relating to the availability of ICT’s and new media applications that can contribute to crisis management. To supplement these findings, in chapter four, partners sought to identify which stakeholders were using these new media applications and whether they were being used in a manner other than that originally intended.

As explained in Chapter 4, it was very difficult to precisely determine which stakeholders were using different types of new media applications. This was particularly evident when trying to determine which stakeholders were using mobile applications. As argued in Chapter 4, there is a need for the further collection of primary data to further understand stakeholder engagement with tools, which is currently beyond the scope of this project, but should be considered an area of research for future activities. From the information that partners were able to identify, there are five categories of stakeholders using new media applications: Government, the media, civil society organisations, industry and the public. Out of these five categories, it appears that civil society organisations, government (and their associated departments) and the public are more readily involved in using new media applications than other stakeholders.

As a final point, Chapter 4 was able to demonstrate that some web based applications and social networking applications were not originally developed to aid crisis response, yet their features are becoming popular, useful tools for crisis management activities.

This report therefore, has been able to provide a baseline analysis of existing information communication technologies and new media applications that are being used in crisis management activities. Crucially, whilst there are many functions that different telecommunications and new media applications are able to offer, it is highly dependent on stakeholders using them to meet their needs in crisis management activities. As outlined in this report, the Internet and other advances in communication technologies have played an important role in enabling different stakeholders to become more active in crisis management activities, in what can be described as contributing to the development of a more participatory approach to crisis communication.

The findings of this report will be used to develop a briefing paper on new media in crisis situations (Deliverable 2.4).

APPENDIX¹³¹

¹³¹ University of San Francisco, no date.

ACRONYMS

A	
ARC	American Red Cross
C	
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
D	
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
E	
EMSC	European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre
EU	European Union
EUROCONTROL	European Organisation for the Safety of Air Navigation
I	
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
N	
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NGO	Non-government organisation
O	
OCHA	Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
Q	
QoS	Quality of Service
S	
SLA	Service level agreement
SMS	Short Message Service
SS7	Signalling System No.7
U	
UN	United Nations
W	
WAP	Wireless Application Protocol
WP	Work Package